

REALIZATION OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF FOLIAR FERTILIZERS BASED ON EXTRACTIONS FROM PEAT

A. DORNEANU¹, M. DUMITRU, Iulia ANTON, Ioana OPRICĂ

Abstract. Peat are a recent sediment on bogs, composed in its majority of crop residues with conserved morphological structure generally, but passed through a chemical and physical process whose result is enrichment in humic substances. Humic substances from peat are mineralized very quickly releasing humates and nutritional elements for plants. So, peat is a valuable organic fertilizer used for crop fertilization, especially into horticulture. Recent methods allow the treatment of peat with alkaline solutions for extract, with low-cost, some humic acids and nutrients that they contain. These extracts sprayed on the plants at a rate of 5-10 l/ha by 2-3 applications during the season growing provide important yield increases.

Keywords: peat, humates, nutritional elements

Introduction

Scientific progress in increasing awareness of the role of humic substances in the development of soil fertility and reducing negative effects on the quality and quantity of humus in the cultivated soils, including those intensively chemically fertilized, stimulated the scientific research concern in various countries for creating new types of humic fertilizers that ensure optimum nutritive satisfaction and amelioration of soil humus (Dorneanu A. și col. 2007).

A main category of raw materials for the production of humic fertilizers at the industrial quantities in our Romania is the peat that is widespread in various humid places especially in hilly and mountainous areas.

It is estimated a peat volume available for the production of humic fertilizer over 80 million m³ (Pop E., 1960 Davidescu et al., 1969).

Academician Emil Pop in his monumental work „Peat swamps in Romania”, in 1960, defined the peat as being a recent sediment mostly composed from vegetal residues maintaining, in general, conserved the morphological structure of plant residues, but passed through a physical and chemical process (process of peat formation) whose main result is a relative enrichment in carbon.

There are two categories of peat important for the production of fertilizers: eutrophic and oligotrophic.

¹National Research and Development Institute for Soil Science, Agrochemistry and Environmental Protection – R.I.S.S.A., Bucharest, Mărăști Street, No. 61, Tel. 00402184349, Fax 0040213184348, e-mail lia_6782000@yahoo.com

Eutrophic peats are formed under growing vegetation in a water saturated substrate, rich in minerals derived from leaching water under the anaerobiosis conditions of soil and water. Peat layer is formed under the infiltrated water (Pop E., 1960).

Floristic composition consists mostly of genus of *Phragmites*, *Typha*, *Scirpus*, *Juncus*, *Carex* and numerous other aquatic species with lower attendance. The appearance of the vegetation is very different, sometimes prevails reed, sometimes sedge, wet meadow or a marsh with brushes. Due to the floristic composition and concentration of infiltrated salt water, eutrophic peats have a humic and mineral composition very different. They contain organic substances in a proportion of 64-87%, 10-21% ash, they have a specific gravity of 1.6-1.8 g/cm³, a calorific value of 1300-2000 kcal/kg. The water content is of 70-75% (Petrescu I. et al. 1986-1987).

This peat is used for the production of fertilizers in the form of mixtures with strong mineral nutrients, or for the extraction of humic acids with potassium hydroxide, sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide. These acids are used to produce different types of foliar or root complex liquid fertilizers mixed with mineral nutrient solutions (Dorneanu A. și col. 2011).

Oligotrophic peats are formed in cold climates rich in precipitation in the Northern Hemisphere, including Northern Europe (including northern Romania) on soils poor in mineral elements (crystalline schist, sandstone, sandy alluvial deposits). The eutrophic swamp (*tinov*) may occur by direct silting of the oligotrophic lake, from a eutrophic swamp passing through a mesotrophic stage or a peaty forest (Pop E., 1960).

Flora is composed of several species of sphagnum moss and slow-growing oligotrophic phanerogamae (Pop E., 1960). Due to the strong mineral sphagnum moss development, the contact with the mineral substrate is highly reduced or discontinued, the only one nutritional source for development being represented by the elementary particles over moorland by winds and rich rainfalls.

Due to the natural development conditions, oligotrophic peats have a more uniform composition than the eutrophic peats, being the same composition everywhere. They have a high content of organic matter (2-98%), very low content of mineral elements (2.3-2.5%) measured in ash, specific gravity of 1.6 g/cm³ and thermal power from 2200 to 2570 kcal/kg. The peats of such a composition can be used very effectively for extracting the humic acids to produce liquid humic complex fertilizers with mixture mineral nutrients (Dorneanu A. și col. 2010).

Materials and methods

Considering the quality of oligotrophic peat for producing humic acids for obtaining various types of foliar complex fertilizers by their mixture with mineral nutrients, the oligotrophic peat from the Poiana Mare enterprise, Suceava County, was used.

The dry matter composition of this peat was: organic matter (OM) - 68.0%, total nitrogen (t_N) - 0.158%, phosphorus (P_2O_5) - 0.0023% and potassium (K_2O) - 0.0265%, pH being 4.58. (Dorneanu A. și col. 2013)

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the compositions of manufactured fertilizers. The content of phosphorous, potassium, magnesium and humic acids is the same in all the types. Differences are only with the nitrogen contents.

The f F-111 and TH5 Bs fertilizers also differ by the addition of the ASFAC-BCO-4an auxine stimulator for plant growth. This bio-stimulator stimulates cell division and increase in cell volume (DORNEANU A. et al., 2013).

All the other 5 fertilizers have been tested in order to differentiate the yield increases versus non-fertilized treatments with different soil types in different climatic zones.

Table 1. Compositions of F-111 TH3, F-111 TH5, F-111 TH10 and F-111 TH5 Bs foliar fertilisers constituted from mixture of humic acids with minerals nutrients (Dorneanu A. și col. 2013).

Item	Components of fertilisers	MU	Fertiliser types			
			F-111 TH3	F-111 TH5	F-111 TH10	F-111 TH5Bs
1.	Total nitrogen (Tn)	%	15,5	18,5	20,5	18,5
2.	Phosphorus (P_2O_5)	%	7,6	7,6	7,6	7,6
3.	Potassium (K_2O)	%	8,9	8,9	8,9	8,9
4.	Magnesium (Mg)	%	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15
5.	Humic acids	%	3,81	3,81	3,81	3,81
6.	ASFAC –BCO4 growing bio-stimulators	%	-	-	-	-

The foliar fertiliser application technology of consisted from three applications during the growing season with a fertiliser solution of 1% in a volume of 500 l/ha solution per treatment.

The obtained results are as follows:

3. Maize grown on Cambic Chernozem receiving a total of 15 l/ha fertilizer reached yield increases between 2327 and 2538 kg kernels/ha, respectively 141.0 - 145.6 f % as compared to the control (Table 2).

4. Potatoes grown on Cambic Chernozem and receiving the same rates obtained increases between 9502 and 9847 kg tubers/ha, respectively 145.7 - 147.4% as compared to the control (Table 3).

5. Tomatoes grown on Argic Phaeozem soil and receiving the same rates obtained increases between 2190 and 3160 kg/ha fruits, respectively 110.4 - 115.0 % as compared to the control (Table 4).

6. Mountain natural grassland on Eutric Cambic soil 2 two applications totalizing 10 l/ha fertilizer of the same types obtained increases ranging between 1560 - 2123 kg dry hay/ha, respectively 122.8 - 132.6% as compared to the control (Table 5).

Table 2. Efficiency of F-111 TH3, F-111 TH5, F-111 TH10 fertilizers applied to the DK 315 maize hybrid grown on Cambic Chernozem at the ICB Iași, experiment field of the USAMV Iași (Bireescu și col., 2012).

Nr. Var.	Treatment	Nr. treat.	Solution concentration %	Quantity of applied fertiliser l (kg)/ha		Kernel production kg/ha	Increase	
				For one application	For all the applications		Kg/ha	%
1.	Non-fertilized control	-	-	-	-	5563	-	100,0
2.	F-111 TH3	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	7890	2327	141.8
3.	F-111 TH5	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	7987	2427	143.5
4.	F-111 TH10	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	8102	2538	145.6

LSD 5%

714

LSD 1%

1256

LSD 0.1%

1565

*Without basic soil fertilization

Table 3. Efficiency of F-111 TH3, F-111 TH5, F-111 TH10 fertilizers applied to the potatoes Sante cultivar grown on Cambic Chernozem at the ICB Iași, experiment field of the USAMV Iași (Bireescu și col., 2012).

Nr. Var.	Treatment	Nr. treat.	Solution concentration %	Quantity of applied fertilizer l (kg)/ha		Yield of potatoes l (kg)/ha	Increase	
				For one application	For all the applications		Kg/ha	%
1.	Non-fertilized control	-	-	-	-	20789	-	100,0
2.	F-111 TH3	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	30385	9596	146.2
3.	F-111 TH5	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	30291	9502	145.7
4.	F-111 TH10	3	1.0	5.0	15.0	30636	9847	147.4

LSD 5%

3086

LSD 1%

4793

LSD 0,1%

6121

*Without basic soil fertilization

Table 4. Efficiency of F-111 TH5, F-111 TH5 Bs**, F-111 TH10 fertilizers applied to tomatoes Romec cultivar grown on Agric Phaeozem at the USAMV Cluj-Napoca, Iernut experiment field (Dorneanu A. și col. 2012).

Treatment	Nr. treat.	Solution concentration %	Quantity of applied fertilizer I (kg/ha) For one application	Yield Of potatoes I (kg)/ha		Fruit increase Kg/ha	Increase	
				For one application	For all the applications		Kg/ha	%
1.	Non-fertilized control	-	-	-	-	21060	-	100,0
2.	F-111 TH5	3	1.0	5.0	10.0	23250	2190	110.4
3.	F-111 TH5 Bs	3	1.0	5.0	10.0	23840	2780	113.2
4.	F-111 TH10	3	1.0	5.0	10.0	24220	3160	115.0

LSD 5%

560

LSD 1%

780

LSD 0,1%

1060

*) Basic soil fertilization with N-80, P₂O₅-80, K₂O-80 Kg/ha

**) Bs = ASFAC –BCO-4 auxinic bio-stimulator

Table 5. Efficiency of F-111 TH3, F-111 TH5, F-111 TH10 fertilizers applied to grassland on mountainous Eutricambosol at the Research- Development Institute for Land grasses - Braşov, Drăguş experiment field, Făgăraş Depression (Dorneanu A. și col. 2012).

Nr. of treatment	Treatment	Nr. of treatment	Solution concentration %	Quantity of applied fertilizer I (kg)/ha		Hay yield d.m. kg/ha	Increase	
				For one application	For all the applications		Kg/ha	%
1.	Non-fertilized control	-	-	-	-	6830	-	100,0
2.	F-111 TH5	2	1,0	5,0	10,0	8390	1560	122,8
3.	F-111 TH5 Bs	2	1,0	5,0	10,0	8410	1580	123,1
4.	F-111 TH10	2	1,0	5,0	10,0	9060	2230	132,6

LSD 5%

1580

LSD 1%

2130

LSD 0.1%

2840

*) Basic soil fertilization with N-50, P₂O₅-50, K₂O-50 Kg/ha

Among the results, the followings are observed:

- all the 4 fertilizers applied at relatively low rates provided significant yield increases which show high efficacy;
- yield increases with all the crops in different climatic zones proved their universal character suitable to be applied for various crops and plant species.

Conclusions

The performed experiences lead to the following conclusions:

1. the complex liquid foliar fertilizers with humic acids from peat represent a new category of fertilizers ensuring a fertilization level under the ecological protection conditions;

2. offers a wide possibility for applying fertilizers in several stages during the growing season (from the occurrence of the first leaf up to the beginning of fructification) by spraying (pulverization) the plant foliage at low amounts on the order of liters or tens of liters per hectare which are assimilated almost completely preventing soil pollution;

3. the nutritive elements incorporated in humic fertilizers are very available for plants. Ions and molecules in these fertilizers are immediately absorbed through the leaves and are metabolized in physiologically active organic compounds that integrate in the general metabolic process causing the intensification of plant growth and development. Foliar uptake rate is much higher than that through the roots (Dorneanu A. și col. 2009).

4. the costs of peats are low and their processing is possible in simple installations with low investment costs both in the farms and small industrial units with the lowest cost of foliar fertilizers;

5. they are available to contain macro and micronutrients, often also additions of growing stimulators can allow the achievement of a large number of fertilizer types that facilitate differentiated fertilizations with minimal costs and maximum efficiency;

6. the peat reserves in Romania,, estimated at over 80 mil. m³ are spread over large hilly and mountainous areas and ensure the necessary raw material without depletion limits for a long period of this resource.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE MIXTURE LUPINE+OAT+RAPE USED LIKE GREEN MANURE UNDER THE MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE SOIL FERTILITY FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE SYSTEM IN NORTH WESTERN ROMANIA

Cornel DOMUȚA¹, Radu BREJEA², Ioana BORZA³

Abstract. The paper is based on the research carried out in a long term trial placed in 2000, on a soil with 10% slope at Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. The research emphasize the improve of the physical (structure degree, bulk density, total porosity, penetration rezistance, hydraulic conductivity) chemical (pH, mineral nitrogen, mobile phosphorum, mobile potassium) and biological properties (actual dehydrogenase activity,potential dehydrogenase activity, catalase activity, acid phosphatise activity, alkaline phosphatase activity) of the soil in the lupin pure crop and especially in the mixture lupine+oat+rape; as consequence this mixture is recomanded.

Keywords: Green manure, lupin, sustainable agriculture

1. Introduction

Sustainable agriculture system is based on the following component: crop rotations (central pivot), large structure of crops, organic fertilizers use, chemical fertilizers use in moderate doses correctly soil tillage, integrated management of the plant protection, resources conservation, the use of the farms interne, resources integration between field crop branch and horticulture or zootechnical branch determine to obtain high yields and the environment is protected. [1,2,3,4,5,6,11,13,14,15,20,24,25,26]. Organic fertilization is difficult to realize because the quantities of the manure produced by farms are small and don't provide an optimum fertilization. The green manure use was stimulated by European Union but establishing the harvest period in March, the use of the rape is encouraged and not the use of the leguminous. One of the most known leguminous was used like green manure is the lupin; the problem of the priming effect produced by the use of the lupin in pure crop was solved by Roger (1976)

¹ Prof., PhD, Researcher, Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Oradea,
(domuta_cornel@yahoo.com)

²Lecturer, PhD, Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Oradea,
(rbrejea@yahoo.com)

³Lecturer, PhD, Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Oradea,
(borzaioanamaria@yahoo.com)

using the mixture vetch + oat (rye) + ryegrass. Vetch is very known like excellent fodder and Domuța C. (1987) starting the research using the mixture lupin +oat, lupin + oat + rape, lupin + rye and the mixture of the lupin determined better results than the mixture of vetch. [16,17,18,19]

2. Material and methods

The research was carried on eroded soil with slope of 10% at Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. In 1999 was placed the experiment with three factors: Factor A: crop rotation, with a_1 = winter wheat – maize; a_2 = oat + clover – clover – maize – winter wheat – maize. Factor B: organic fertilization with b_1 = control, without fertilizers; b_2 = *Lupinus angustifolius*; b_3 = *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape; b_4 = vetch + oat + ryegrass; b_5 = manure, 25 t/hectare; b_6 = manure, 50 t/hectare. Factor C: annual chemical fertilization: c_1 = N_0P_0 ; c_2 = $N_{120}P_{90}$. Number of repetition used: 4. The lot surface: 100 m².

In 2013, after winter wheat harvesting, a soil profile was made in the first crop rotation and the cylinders with soil were prelevated for determination in the laboratory, of the bulk density (BD), hydraulic conductivity and penetration resistance (PR); the cylinders were prelevated on a 0 - 10 cm depth and 10 – 20 cm depth and the averages on the 0 – 20 cm are presented in the papers. Other soil samples were prelevated on 0 – 20 cm depth for determination the structure degree, mineral nitrogen, pH, mobile phosphorus, mobile potassium. The soil samples for enzymatic activity determination were prelevated on 0-10 cm, 10-20 cm and 20-30 cm. The following enzymological parameters were: actual and potential dehydrogenase, catalase activity, acid and alkaline phosphatase activity. The usually methods were used for all determinations. [9,10,12,14,27,29,30,31]

Soil reaction was determined by potentiometer method; mobile phosphorus and mobile potassium were determined by Egner – Rhiem – Domingo method. Four repetition were realized for every physical and chemical parameters and the research results were interpreted by variance analysis method. [7,8,21,22,23]

3. Results and discussions

Structure degree

The smallest value of the structure degree was determined in the variant without organic fertilization, 54.70%; the result obtained in the variant *Lupinus angustifolius* like green manure is very close, 54.50%. In the variant with the mixture *Lupinus angustifolius*+ oat +rape, the structure degree increase significant statistically in comparison with control. (Table 1).

Bulk density and total porosity

All the variants with organic fertilization determined the decrease of the bulk density values in comparison with the control (1.52g/cm³), 8% in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* (significant statistically), 12% in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape (distingue significant statistically). (Table 2).

Table 1.The influence of the green manure and manure on structure degree of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	Structure degree		Difference %	Statistically significant
	Val %	%		
1. Control	54.70	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	54.50	99	-1	-
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	58.80	108	8	*

LSD 5% 3.96%; LSD 1% 6.02%; LSD 0.1% 13.56%

Table 2.The influence of the green manure and manure on bulk density (BD) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2003

Variant	BD		Difference	Statistically significant
	g/cm ³	%		
1. Control	1.52	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	1.0	92	-8	0
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	1.35	88	-12	00

LSD 5% 0.10; LSD 1% 0.15; LSD 0.1% 0.21

Total porosity

Calculating the total porosity the smallest value was obtained in the control, 43%. The difference registered in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* (9%) is insignificant statistically. It was registered a difference of 14% in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape (significant statistically). (Table 3).

Table 3.The influence of the green manure and manure on total porosity (TP) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	TP		Difference (%)	Statistically Significant
	%	%		
1. Control	43	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	47	109	9	-
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	49	114	14	*

LSD 5% 4.5; LSD 1% 7.5; LSD 0.1% 11.0

Penetration rezistance

The biggest value of the penetration rezistance 25.0 kgf/cm², was registered in the control; in the variants with organic fertilization, the values of penetration rezistance decreased; the differences were distingue significant statistically. (Table 4).

Hydraulic conductivity

The hydraulic conductivity had the smallest value in the control. In the variant with green manure pure crop, the hydraulic conductivity increased with 17% (unsignificant statistically); in variant with mixture *Lupinus angustifolius*+rape, the increase was significant statistically. (Table 5)

Table 4.The influence of the green manure and manure on penetration rezistance (PR) of the eroded soil from Oradea,2013

Variant	PR		Difference (%)	Statistically significant
	Kg/cm ²	%		
1. Control	25.0	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	19.8	79	-21	00
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	18.9	76	-24	00

LSD 5% 3.5; LSD 1% 6.3; LSD 0.1% 11.30

Table 5.The influence of the green manure and manure on hydraulic conductivity (HC) of the eroded soil from Oradea,2 013

Variant	HC		Difference (%)	Statistically significant
	mm/h	%		
1. Control	13.30	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	15.58	117	17	-
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	16.47	124	24	-

LSD 5% 2.70; LSD 1% 4.72; LSD 0.1% 7.29

Soil reaction

The value of the pH determined in the control was of 6.3. The values determined in the studies variants are very close and to control but the difference are unsignificant statistically (Table 6).

Table 6.The influence of the green manure and manure on the pH of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	pH		Difference	Statistically significant
	Value	%		
1. Control	6.30	100	-	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	6.29	99	-1	-
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	6.32	101	+1	-

LSD 5% 0.13; LSD 1% 0.24; LSD 0.1% 0.40

Mineral nitrogen

The value of the N – NO₃ determined in the control was of 0,70 ppm. The difference registered in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* (64%) was distinguishable statistically. In the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape the difference are very significant statistically. (Table 7).

The N – NH₄ content is bigger than N – NO₃ content in the variants. In the control was registered the smallest value, 2.6 ppm.

In the all variants with organic fertilization the N-NH₃ the content was very significant bigger.

The content of N – NO₃ + NH from the control is of 3.16 ppm. The values of the N – NO₃ + NH₄ from the variants with organic fertilization are bigger than the value determined in the control; the biggest difference, 94%, was registered in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape (Table 7).

Table 7. The influence of the green manure and manure on the N – NO₃+ N – NH₄ of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	N – NO ₃			N – NH ₄			N – NO ₃ + NH ₄		
	ppm	%	Statistically significant	ppm	%	Statistically significant	ppm	%	Statistically significant
1. Control	0.70	100	Control	2.46	100	Control	3.16	100	Control
2. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>	1.15	164	**	3.82	153	***	4.97	157	***
3. <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> + oat + rape	1.20	172	***	4.94	201	***	6.14	194	***

LSD 5% 0.17

LSD 1% 0.28

LSD 0.1% 0.51

LSD 5% 0.60

LSD 1% 0.64

LSD 0.1% 1.12

LSD 5% 0.23

LSD 1% 0.46

LSD 0.1% 0.81

Mobile phosphorus

The mobile phosphorus is median in the control (34.6 ppm) and good in the others variants.

The differences registered in comparison, with the control are insignificant statistically. (Table 8).

Table 8. The influence of the green manure and manure on mobile phosphorus (PAL) content of eroded soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	PAL		Difference	Statistically significant
	ppm	%		
1. Control	34.6	100	-	Control
2. Lupinus angustifolius	37.8	109	9	-
3. Lupinus angustifolius + oat + rape	39.0	113	13	-

LSD 5% 7.8; LSD 1% 12.6; LSD 0,1% 21.3

Mobile potassium

The smallest content of the mobile potassium was registered in the control, 196.2 ppm.

The differences registered in the variants with green manure and in the variant with manure 27 t/hectare are insignificant statistically. (Table 9).

Table 9. The influence of the green manure and manure on mobile potassium (KAL content of the preluco soil from Oradea, 2013

Variant	KAL		Difference	Statistically significant
	ppm	%		
1. Control	192.2	100	-	Control
2. Lupinus angustifolius	199.3	102	2	-
3. Lupinus angustifolius + oat + rape	204.7	104	4	-

LSD 5% 13.2; LSD 1% 18.4; LSD 0.1% 27.8

Actual dehydrogenase activity

The values of the actual dehydrogenase activity are bigger on the depth of 0 – 10 cm in comparison with the one on 10 – 20 cm and 20 – 30 cm. The smallest value of the actual dehydrogenase activity were determined in the variant without fertilizer: 5.50 mg TPF/24 hours on 0 – 10 cm, 4.51mg TPF/24 hours on 10 – 20 cm and 2.72 mg TPF/24 hours on 20 -30 cm.

The use of the manure and green manure determined a bigger value of the actual dehydrogenase activity, in average on the depth of 0 - 30 cm, in comparison with the variant without fertilizers, the use of Lupinus angustifolius used as a green manure determined an increase with 66%, insignificant from a statistical

point of view. In the variant with a mixture of *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape the actual dehydrogenase activity increased with 116%, significantly statistically. (Table 10).

Table 10. Green manure influence on actual dehydrogenase activity (ADA) on the eroded soil from Oradea 2013

Variant	ADA		Diffrence %	Sstatistically significant
	mgTPF/24 h	%		
Depth 0 – 10 cm				
1.Control	5.50	100	-	control
2. Lupin	9.18	167	67	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	11.62	212	112	x
LSD 5% 3.27		LSD 1% 6.74		LSD 0.1% 10.90
Depth 10 – 20 cm				
1.Control	4.51	100	-	control
2. Lupin	7.06	157	57	-
3.Lupin +oat + rape	10.20	227	127	x
LSD 5% 3.60		LSD 1% 6.90		LSD 0.1 11.20
Depth 20 – 30 cm				
1.Control	2.72	100	-	control
2. Lupin	4.90	181	81	-
3.Lupin +oat + rape	5.76	212	112	x
LSD 5% 2.28		LSD 1% 4.70		LSD 0.1% 6.76
Average Deapth 0 – 30 cm				
1.Control	4.25	100	-	control
2. Lupin	7.05	166	66	-
3.Lupin +oat + rape	9.20	216	116	x
LSD 5% 3.05		LSD 1% 6.14		LSD 0.1% 9.62

Potential dehydrogenase activity (PDA)

The values of the potential dehydrogenase activity were bigger than the value of the actual dehydrogenase activity and decreased together with the increase of the determination depth. The smallest set of values of the potential dehydrogenase activity were determined in the variant without fertilizers: 10.56 TPF/24 h on 0 - 10 cm, 9.31 mg TPF/24 h on 10 - 20 cm and 7.88 mg TPF/24 h on 20 - 30 cm. In average on the 0 – 30 cm depth the value of potential dehydrogenase activity was of 9.25 mg TPF/24 h; the green manures determined a significant increase compared with the control. The increases were of 67% in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* and 98% in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* +oat+rape. (Table 11).

Table 11. Green manure influence on potential dehydrogenase activity (PDA) on the eroded soil from Oradea 2012

Variant	PDA		Difference %	Statistically significant
	mgTPF/24 h	%		
Depth 0 – 10 cm				
1.Control	10.56	100	-	control
2. Lupin	22.68	215	115	xx
3.Lupin +oat + rape	24.18	229	129	xx
LSD 5% 4.20		LSD 1% 9.72		LSD 0.1% 14.20
Depth 10 – 20 cm				
1.Control	9.3	100	-	control
2. Lupin	15.30	165	65	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	16.66	179	79	x
LSD 5% 3.60		LSD 1% 7.85		LSD 0.1% 12.40
Depth 20 – 30 cm				
1.Control	7.88	100	-	Control
2. Lupin	8.33	107	7	-
3.Lupin +oat + rape	14.30	182	82	x
LSD 5% 3.52		LSD 1% 7.60		LSD 0.1% 12.02
Average Deapth 0 – 30 cm				
1.Control	9.25	100	-	control
2. Lupin	15.44	167	67	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	18.38	198	98	x
LSD 5% 3.78		LSD 1% 8.39		LSD 0.1% 12.88

Catalase activity (CA)

Catalase activity decreases according with the increase of the depth determination. The green manure determined bigger values of the catalase activity in comparison with the control; the differences were statistically assured.

In the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* the catalase activity increased with 145%. In the variant *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape the difference in comparison with the control was of 107%. (Table 12).

Table 12. Green manures influence on catalase activity (CA) on the eroded soil from Oradea 2013

Variant	CA		Difference %	Statistically significant
	mg H ₂ O ₂ /1 h	%		
Depth 0 – 10 cm				
1.Control	0.80	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.96	245	145	xx
3.Lupin +oat +rape	2.40	300	200	xxx
LSD 5% 0.25		LSD 1% 0.41		LSD 0.1% 0.96
Depth 10 – 20 cm				
1.Control	0.73	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.70	233	133	xx
3.Lupin +oat +rape	2.20	302	202	xxx
LSD 5% 0.31		LSD 1% 0.72		LSD 0.1% 1.15
Depth 20 – 30 cm				
1.Control	0.61	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.60	263	163	xx
3.Lupin +oat +rape	2.01	330	230	xxx
LSD 5% 0.33		LSD 1% 0.76		LSD 0.1% 1.27
Average Deapth 0 – 30 cm				
1.Control	0.72	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.76	245	145	xx
3.Lupin +oat +rape	2.21	307	207	xxx
LSD 5% 0.30		LSD 1% 0.63		LSD 0.1% 1.13

Acid phosphatase activity (AcPA)

The values of the acid phosphatase activity decreases according with the increase of the determination depth but the differences are smaller than the differences registred in the previous enzymological parameters.

The smallest values of the acid phosphatase activity were registred in the control: 2.60 mg phenyl/ g soil/ 2h on 0 -10 cm; 2.30 mg phenyl/ g soil/ 2h on 10 - 20 cm and 2.2 mg mg phenyl/ g soil/ 2h on 20 - 30 cm.

In average on the 0 - 30 cm in comparison with the control 2.38 mg phenyl/ g soil/ 2h, a signifiant result from a statistical point of view is *Lupinus angustifolius* (15%). The variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat + rape registred 20%. (Table 13).

Table 13. Green manures influence on acid phosphatase activity (AcPA) on the eroded soil from Oradea 2013

Variant	AcPA		Difference %	Statistically significant
	mg phenol/g soil/2 h	%		
Depth 0 – 10 cm				
1.Control	2.60	100	--	control
2. Lupin	2.80	108	8	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	2.92	105	5	xx
LSD 5% 0.19		LSD 1% 0.34		LSD 0.1% 0.60
Depth 10 – 20 cm				
1.Control	2.30	100	-	control
2. Lupin	2.74	120	20	xx
3.Lupin +oat + rape	2.85	124	24	xx
LSD 5% 0.17		LSD 1% 0.29		LSD 0.1% 0.57
Depth 20 – 30 cm				
1.Control	2.22	100	-	control
2. Lupin	2.68	121	21	xx
3.Lupin +oat + rape	2.73	123	23	xx
LSD 5% 0.20		LSD 1% 0.34		LSD 0.1% 0.62
Average Deapth 0 – 30 cm				
1.Control	2.38	100	-	control
2. Lupin	2.74	115	15	xx
3.Lupin +oat + rape	2.84	120	20	xx
LSD 5% 0.19		LSD 1% 0.33		LSD 0.1% 0.60

Alkaline phosphatase activity (AlkPa)

The values of alkaline phosphatase activity were smaller than the values of the acid phosphatase activity and decreased with the depth of the collected sample.

The smallest values of the alkaline phosphatase activity were registered in the variant used as control. In average the value of the alkaline phosphatase activity on the depth of 0 - 30 cm was 1.29 mg phenyl /g soil/ 2 h. In the variants with green manure the values were bigger than the control.

The difference for *Lupinus angustifolius* in pure crop was 19%, significant statistically. (Table 14).

Table 14. Green manures influence on alkaline phosphatase activity (CA) on the eroded soil from Oradea 2013

Variant	AlkPa		Difference %	Statistically significant
	mg phenol/g soil/2 h	%		
Depth 0 – 10 cm				
1.Control	1.36	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.68	124	24	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	1.96	144	44	xxx
LSD 5% 0.18		LSD 1% 0.37		LSD 0.1% 0.61
Depth 10 – 20 cm				
1.Control	1.32	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.52	116	16	-
3.Lupin +oat + rape	1.69	128	28	xx
LSD 5% 0.17		LSD 1% 0.29		LSD 0.1% 0.54
Depth 20 – 30 cm				
1.Control	1.20	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.39	116	16	x
3.Lupin +oat + rape	1.52	127	27	x
6. Manure 50 t/ha	1.67	140	40	xx
LSD 5% 0.15		LSD 1% 0.27		LSD 0.1% 0.58
Average Depth 0 – 30 cm				
1.Control	1.29	100	-	control
2. Lupin	1.53	119	19	X
3.Lupin +oat + rape	1.73	134	34	xx
LSD 5% 0.17		LSD 1% 0.31		LSD 0.1% 0.58

Conclusions

The research carried out in a long term trial from the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea permitted the following conclusions:

(1) physical parameters of the soil were improved in the variants with green manure in comparison with the control: bulk density and penetration resistance decreased, total porosity and hydraulic conductivity increased; a more favourable values were obtained in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape in comparison with *Lupinus angustifolius*, pure crop. Regarding the soil structure degree, in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* pure crop, a little smaller value was registered in comparison with the control but in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape the value of the structure degree is bigger than the value registered in the control;

(2) regarding the soil chemical properties the different situation were registered: the pH value didn't determinate the differences statistically assured in the variants with organic fertilization in comparison with the control; the N-NO₃ + NH₄ content are bigger in the variant with green manure in comparison with the manure. In comparison with the value determinate in the control, 3.16 ppm, in the all variants studied were registered the differences very significant statistically; mobile phosphorus and potassium content increased in the variants with green manures in comparison with the control;

(3) enzymological activity (actual and potential dehydrogenase, catalase activity, acid and alkaline phosphatase activity) were the smallest values in the control, the enzymological activity increased in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius* pure crop but the biggest values were registered in the variant with *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape;

The result research sustain the use of the lupin like green manure mixture crop (*Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape) because the lupin is known for this destination and don't sustain the use of the *Lupinus angustifolius*, pure crop.

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THE MAIN FEATURES OF ROMANIA'S AGRICULTURE IN THE PERIOD 2007-2012

Agatha POPESCU¹

Abstract. Romania has a high agricultural potential but it is not enough utilized. Agricultural production increased but not enough, being still huge differences compared to the EU yields and production. The number of 3,859,043 farms is the largest in the EU (32%) and 3.57 ha/farm in average do not allow the application of modern technologies. The low technical endowment in the subsistence and semisubsistence farms is characterized by Euro 540/farm average fixed assets, 5.10 % irrigated land of the available surface, the low amount of fertilizers and huge charge of land per tractor, 54.1 ha. About 30 % of population is employed in agriculture. Rural population is characterized by aging, low training level and income, young generation is moving to cities looking for better paid jobs, the lack of diversified activities does not provide jobs and more revenues. However, important improvements have been noticed regarding agricultural production value, mainly due to the vegetal sector which has been rapidly developed. The contribution of agriculture to GDP increased by 19 % in the period 2007-2012, but its share in Romania's GDP declined to 4.88%.

Key words: agriculture, features, Romania

1. Introduction

Agriculture has a very important role in the economy: it provides food for population and raw materials major industries, it supplies fodder for animal husbandry, employment opportunities and income for the people living in the rural areas, it encourage the development of living standard in the rural space, it gives its contribution to GDP, and has a good play in international trade with agro-food products contributing to a better distribution of food and raw materials at world level, it brings important foreign currency to reduce the unfavorable balance of payments, and also it assures food security. (Stringer, 2001, Meijerink and Roza, 2007).

But the economists are focused on how agriculture could give more contribution to overall development and modernization (Johnston and Mellor (1961).

The traditional approach regarding the role of agriculture is based on the following aspects: to provide raw materials for agro-processing industries, to provide labor for industry sector in the urban areas, to produce food for covering

¹ Prof.Ph.D., University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania, (e_mail: agatha_popescu@yahoo.com)

population needs, to supply savings for investments in industry, to extend markets for industrial products, to bring earnings from export in order to pay imported goods (Johnston and Mellor, 1961; Timmer, 1992).

FAO initiated in 2001 the Role of Agriculture Project (ROA) as a new approach of the role of agriculture to poverty alleviation and socio-economic development. (FAO, 2001).

However, the development of urbanization and industries has led to a decline of agriculture contribution to GDP and to the reduction of population in the rural space, mainly the young generation being more interested to look for better paid jobs in the cities. The modern technologies applied in agriculture have increased labor productivity and product quality, increased value added per agricultural worker. Climate change has become a restraining factor in agriculture if corresponding measures are not taken to diminish its negative effects on production systems. (Meijerink and Roza, 2007).

After 1990, Romania's agriculture passed to a new era facing important transformation in farm structures, agricultural systems, production performances and its role in the economy. (Zahiu *et al.*, 2010, Otiman, 2012).

Romania's accession into the EU structures in 2007 has also changed the agricultural policy paying more attention to fulfill the requirements of the PAC. In this context, the paper aimed to analyze the statement of agriculture after the year 2007 when Romania has become an E.U. member state and to identify the main features represented by agrarian structure characterized by the number of agricultural holdings and farm size, technical endowment in agriculture characterized by fixed assets, number of tractors and number of tractors per ha, amount of chemical and organic fertilizers, irrigated agricultural land, net investments, cereal production as the main performance in the agricultural production, employment in agriculture and labor productivity, agricultural production value and contribution of agriculture to GDP.

2. Materials and methods

In order to identify the main features of the Romanian agriculture, the following aspects have been approached: number of agricultural holdings and farms size, fixed assets, number of tractors and number of tractors per ha, fertilizers, irrigated land, net investments, employed population in agriculture, labor productivity, cereal production, agricultural production value, agriculture contribution to GDP.

The analysis was carried out for the period 2007-2012 and was based on the data provided by Romania's Statistical Yearbook, 2013.

3. Results and discussions

Number of agricultural holdings. Romania has the highest number of agricultural holdings in the EU, in 2010, accounting for 3,859,043 units, by 1.84 % less than in the year 2007.(3,931,350 units).

In the year 2010, of the total number of agricultural holdings, about 99.06 %, that is the largest number, was represented by individual agricultural holdings, working about 65 % of the total utilized agricultural land. The remaining of 30,698 units with juridical personality accounted for 0.94% of the total number of agricultural holdings and were working about 35 % of the utilized agricultural (Table 1).

Table 1. The statement of the agricultural holdings in Romania in 2007 and 2010

Specification	2007	2010	2010/2007
Total agricultural holdings, of which:	3,931,350	3,859,043	98.16
-Individual agricultural holdings	3,913,651	3,823,130	97.68
-Units with juridical personality	17,699	30,698	173.44

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

The Romanian agricultural holdings represent the largest number of farms in the EU, accounting for about 32 % of the total number of farms in the community. Romania is followed by Italy with about 13.5 %, Poland with 12.5 %, Spain with about 8.2 %. All these 4 countries have 66.2 % of the whole number of farms in the EU (Alecu Ioan Nicolae, 2013, Popescu Agatha, 2014).

Average farm size. In the year 2010, the average agricultural land per farm accounted for 3.57 ha by 2 % more than in the year 2007, when the farm size was 3.5 ha in average. The individual farms recorded 2.02 ha in average compared to 190.78 ha/farm in case of the commercial holdings. The main trend is a decreasing one in the both cases because in the year 2010 the farm size was smaller by 12.18 % in case of individual farms and by 29.45 % in case of the units with juridical personality (Table 2).

Table 2. Average farm size in Romania in 2007 and 2010 (ha/farm)

Specification	2007	2010	2010/2007
Average farm size at country level	3.5	3.57	102.00
Average size of individual farms	2.3	2.02	87.82
Average size of commercial farms	270.4	190.78	70.55

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

Farm size in Romania is very small reflecting a low efficiency and production performance. Even in the EU, the average of farm size is small, only about 14 ha, but much higher than in Romania. Only Cyprus has a similar farm size, about 3 ha/farm. In Greece and Slovenia, farms have about 6 ha. The countries with an average farms size between 55-65 ha are: France, Germany, Luxembourg and Denmark, where agriculture is highly developed. Also, we can not compared Romania's average farm size with the one from United Kingdom, 79 ha, and from Czech Republic, 152 ha, the highest in the EU. (Eurostat, Farm structure statistics, 2000-2010 and Popescu Agatha, 2014).

The small farm size requires association between various agricultural producers, the setting up of producers' groups and new commercial companies according to the legislation in force in order to join the capital and be able to cultivated land in a more efficient way, applying modern technologies in order to increase agricultural prpduction and its quality, labor productivity and farm competitiveness.

Fixed assets. Technical endowment with fixed assets in agriculture is very important. In the year 2012, the value of fixed assets existing in agriculture of Romania accounted for Lei million 32,926.7, being 2.15 times higher than in the year 2007. However, in the period 2007-2012, the share of fixed assets belonging to agriculture in the value of fixed assets existing in the national economy varied from a year to another. The highest weight was recorded in the year 2012, 2.33 % while the lowest share was registered in the year 2011, only 1.44 %. (Table 3).

Table 3. Fixed assets in Romania's agriculture, 2007-2012 (Lei million, current prices)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/ 2007
Fixed assets in agriculture, forestry and fishing	15,267.4	25,770.0	33,704.4	28,779.0	40,039.0	32,926.7	215.66
Share in national economy(%)	1.66	1.91	2.27	1.84	1.44	2.33	140.36

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

The level of fixed assets in the Romanian agriculture is still very low compared to other E.U. countries. In Romania, there are allotted only Euro 540 fixed assets per agriculturist, 16-17 times less than in the EU, where an agriculturist has at his disposal about Euro 9,000-9,200 (Otiman, 2012). This has a deep impact on the technological and performance level registered in Romania. Therefore, the lack of fixed assets at a corresponding level is a restraining factor for the Romanian agriculture.

Number of tractors. The Romanian agriculture has still a reduced number of tractors which has a negative impact regarding the quality of agricultural works and the moment when they are carried out. In the analyzed period, the number of tractors increased by 6 % from 174,003 pieces in the year 2007 to 184,446 pieces in the year 2012, which is a positive aspect.

Taking into account the land surface worked by a tractor, one may notice that it is still very high compared to other EU countries. Compared to the year 2007, when a tractor worked 54.1 ha arable land, in the year 2012 the surface allotted per tractor accounted for 50.23 ha, being by 7.16 % lower than in 2007, which is a positive trend.(Table 4).

Table 4. Number of tractors in Romania's agriculture and arable land per tractor, 2007-2012

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/2007
Number of tractors (pieces)	174,003	174,790	176,841	180,433	183,064	184,446	106.00
Arable land per tractor (ha/tractor)	54.1	53.7	53.1	52.11	51.23	50.23	92.84

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013,Own calculations

Fertilizers. The amount of chemical fertilizers used in the Romanian agriculture is still very small compared to the one applied in other EU countries. However, in the year 2012, it was applied an amount of 438 thousand tones, by 13.17 % more than in the year 2007. Also, important amounts of organic fertilizers are available for agriculture, its level being closely related to the number of livestock. In 2012, the amount of organic fertilizers accounted for 123,293 thousand tones, being by 1.52 % lower than in the year 2007 (Table 5).

Table 5. Fertilizers in Romania's agriculture, 2007-2012 (Thousand tones)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/2007
Chemical fertilizers, active substance	387	398	426.2	481	487	438	113.17
Organic fertilizers	13,498	11,748	13,748.3	15,232	14,510	13,293	98.48

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013,Own calculations

Irrigations. Irrigations are a very important factor for production growth in agriculture.

Table 6. Irrigated land in Romania's agriculture, 2007-2012 (Thousand ha)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/2007
Irrigated land	320.2	225.0	296.7	79.21	103.3	161.3	50.37
Land prepared to be irrigated	3,155.3	3,157.1	3,157.04	3,157	3,157	3,157	100.05
% of prepared land	10.0	7.1	9.6	2.51	3.27	5.10	51 %

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

The climate change and global warming have become more and more visible in Romania bringing droughts every year, affecting agricultural production. Despite that the surface prepared for irrigation accounts for 3,157 thousand ha, only 5.10 % was irrigated in the year 2012, representing a half of the irrigated land in 2007.

Therefore, the Romanian agriculture is less irrigated than it needs and much below its potential. (Table 6).

Net investments. Agriculture is an attractive field for investments. The value of net investments increased by 53.38 % from Lei million 2,192.2 in the year 2007 to Lei million 3,362.4 in the year 2012. The share of the net investments in agriculture represented 2.62 % in 2007 and 3.74 % in the value of net investments at national level (Table 7).

Table 7. Net investments in Romania's agriculture, 2007-2012 (Lei million, current prices)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/2007
Net investments in agriculture, forestry and fishing	2,192.2	3,393.3	2,919.5	2,659.5	3,285.1	3,362.4	153.38
Share in national economy(%)	2.62	3.40	3.89	3.67	3.74	3.74	142.74

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

However, investments in the Romanian agriculture are still pale. The borrowings taken from banks by the Romanian farmers are very small, in average Euro 110/ha, while in other EU countries they account for about Euro 1,700-2,000 per ha (Otiman, 2012).

Cereal production. As a main indicator of agriculture development, cereal production is important to be analyzed. In the period 2007-2012, the land cultivated with cereals increased by 4.40 % from 5,129 thousand ha in 2007 to 5,440.3 thousand ha in 2012. Cereal production recorded an important growth from 7,814.8 thousand tons in 2007 to

12,824 thousand tons in the year 2012, when it was by 64 % higher than in the first year of the analysis. As production increased more rapidly than cultivated land with cereals, this means that average production was the key factor which determined this performance. (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, November 2010)

However, cereal production registered various performances in the analyzed period. The maximum cereal production was recorded in the year 2011 because it was a favorable year for agriculture, while in the year 2007 the production level was the lowest one due to the terrible drought registered in Romania. Therefore, Romania has a high potential for producing cereals, except the dry years (Table 8).

Table 8. Cultivated land with cereals and cereal production in Romania, 2007-2012

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2012/ 2007
Cultivated land with cereals (Thousand ha)	5,129. 2	5,210. 7	5,282. 4	5,066. 4	5,224. 7	5,440. 3	106.06
Cereal production (Thousand tons)	7,814. 8	16,826 .4	14,873	16,713	20,842	12,824	164.09

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

Even thou cereal production increased, its level is still very low compared to the one registered by other EU countries. Low technological endowment, and lack of capital caused as the cereal production in Romania to be by 40-45 % smaller than in the EU.(Otiman, 2012).

Employed population in agriculture. Compared to other EU countries, in the Romanian agriculture are employed many persons, as about 30 % of Romania's population is living in the rural areas. In 2011, a number of 2,723.5 thousand persons were employed in the field of agriculture, forestry and fishing, by 4 % less than in the year 2004, which could be considered a positive aspect. In 2011, the employed population in agriculture represented 29.98 % of employed population at national level compared to 30.29 % in the year 2007.(Table 9).

Table 9. Employed population in Romania's agriculture, forestry and fishing, 2007-2012 (Thousand persons)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2011/ 2007 %
Employed persons in agriculture	2,836. 7	2,767. 8	2,764. 2	2,896. 2	2,723. 5	-	96.00
% of employment at national level	30.29	29.55	30.10	31.63	29.98	-	98.97

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

Romania is on the top position in the EU with the highest number of employed persons in agriculture (35%), being followed by Poland (14%), Greece (12%), Portugal (11%) and Spain (10%). (Eurostat FSS, Agricultural Census, 2012, Popescu Agatha, 2013, Popescu Marin, 2009).

Beside the fact that the percentage of population employed in agriculture is very high compared to other EU countries, it is important to mention that in the rural areas, population is facing with aging, a low training level and the movement of young people to cities looking for better paid jobs. Just a few number of the Romanian farmers have a corresponding knowledge level and managerial skills. Most of the farmers own subsistence and semisubsistence farms, lacked of capital and modern technologies.

Labor productivity. In the Romanian agriculture, labor productivity increased by 66.13% from Lei 8,032 per employed person in the year 2007 to Lei 13,343.7 per employed person in the year 2011. The share of employed people in agriculture, forestry and fishing in the employment at national level increased from 20.41% in 2007 to 24.84% in 2012. (Table 10).

Table 10. Labor productivity in Romania's agriculture, forestry and fishing, 2007-2012 (Lei/Employed person)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2011/ 2007 %
Labor productivity in agriculture	8,032	12,329 .8	11,684 .3	10,315 .0	13,343 .7	-	166.13
% in labor productivity in the national economy	20.41	25.18	23.78	20.24	24.84	-	121.70

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

Even though the statistical figures reflect an improved situation of labor productivity in agriculture, in terms of Lei per employed person, these figures cover the real situation, which should be analyzed by the amount of products resulting per working hour.

Agricultural production value increased by 34.71% from Lei million 47,699.9 in the year 2007 to Lei million 64,259.4 in the year 2012 which is a positive aspect. The vegetal production is well represented registering the highest growth in the analyzed period, 39.84%. On the second position came animal production with 28.77% and on the last one agricultural services which recorded a deep decline. (Table 11).

The contribution of various sectors to agricultural production value was the following one: in the year 2007: 60.21% vegetal production, 38.34% animal production and 1.45% agricultural services; in the year 2012: 62.51% vegetal production, 36.65% animal production and 0.84% agricultural services. The weight of the three sectors varied from a year to another. The highest share of 70.81% in agricultural production value was

performed by vegetal production in the year 2011. However, animal production should be better represented and also the percentage of agricultural services is still very low.

Table 11. Agricultural production value in Romania, 2007-2012 (Lei million, current prices)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2011/ 2007 %
Agricultural production value, of which:	47,699.9	66,993.9	59,928.4	64,452.5	76,508.8	64,259.4	134.71
-Vegetal production	28,723.4	45,742.2	35,735.5	43,488.4	54,179.8	40,169.1	139.84
-Animal production	18,291.6	20,535.7	23,441.6	20,406.8	21,784.1	23,555.3	128.77
-Agricultural services	684.8	716.0	751.6	557.2	544.7	535.0	78.12
Share of vegetal production (%)	60.21	68.27	59.63	67.47	70.81	62.51	-
Share of animal production (%)	38.34	30.65	39.11	31.66	28.47	36.65	-
Share of services (%)	1.45	1.08	1.26	0.87	0.72	0.84	-

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

The agricultural production value is still very low compared to the one registered in other EU countries because of the performances per surface unit. In 2012, the value of primary agricultural production accounted for Euro 800-900/ha in Romania compared to Euro 1,800-2,000 in the EU (Otiman, 2012).

Agriculture contribution. The GDP created in agriculture, forestry and fishing increased by 19.49 % from Lei million 23,966.3 in the year 2007 to Lei million 28,638.1 in the year 2012. As a result, the contribution of agriculture to GDP was different from a year to another, and in 2012 accounted for 4.88 % compared to 5.75 % in the year 2007.(Table 12).

Table 12. Agriculture contribution to Romania's GDP (Lei million, current prices)

Specification	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2011/ 2007 %
Agriculture contribution to GDP	23,966.3	34,403.9	32,297.8	29,874.2	36,341.6	28,638.1	119.49
% of GDP	5.75	6.68	6.44	5.70	6.52	4.88	84.86

Source: Statistical Yearbook, 2013, Own calculations

Agriculture contribution to GDP reflect how important is this economic branch in Romania's economy (Zahiu Letitia et al, 2010).

Conclusions

1. Romania has a high agricultural potential which is not yet entirely utilized. Agricultural production is still low compared to other EU countries due to the large number of small farms, their low technical endowment, and farmers' lack of capital, training and managerial skills.

2. Even though the number of agricultural holdings is decreasing, with 3,859,043 farms in 2010, Romania keeps 32% of the whole number of the EU agricultural units.

3. The average farm size, 3.57 ha/farm in 2012, is very small compared to 14 ha/farm the EU average, reflecting a low efficiency and production performance.

4. The value of fixed assets accounted for Lei million 32,926.7 in 2012, being 2.15 times higher than in the year 2007, which is a positive aspect. But a Romanian farmer has still only Euro 540 fixed assets compared to Euro 9,000-9,200 in the EU.

5. The reduced number of tractors, fertilizers, irrigated agricultural land and investments continue to maintain a low productivity, product quality and competitiveness of the Romanian farms.

6. The high number of employed people in agriculture, the lack of diversified activities, aging, low training level and movement of young generation to cities for getting a job reflect the main social aspects the rural space is facing at present and also the low productivity and value added created in agriculture, even though during the last years it was noticed an improvement, but the growth process is still very slow.

7. Agricultural production value increased, but mainly due to the growth of vegetal production, and animal and services sectors are not yet enough developed.

8. The contribution of agriculture to GDP increased by 19%, but is recorded a low decline keeping 4.88 % in Romania's GDP.

9. As a final conclusion, policy makers have to pay more attention to the role of agriculture in the economy to provide high quality food and cover the domestic market demand, to earn income from agro-food products export mainly in the EU countries, to create jobs by diversifying activities in the rural areas and encouraging producers' association to better use their fixed and financial capital and implement modern technologies, to produce more primary materials for processing industries, to create savings for investments for its own development.

10. Agriculture has to be more involved in providing indirect non-commodity contributions such as environmental services regarding water, biodiversity preservation, carbon sequestration, food security, poverty reduction and social viability in the rural space.

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STUDIES ON *DROSOPHILA MELANOGASTER* L. ROMANIAN ECOTYPES HIGHLIGHT THE DIFFERENCES AMONG *DROSOPHILA* ECOTYPES ASSESSING THE MORPHOLOGICAL TRAITS AFTER TRAPPING

Gallia BUTNARU¹, Ioan SARAC¹

Abstract. In comparison with three standard *Drosophila* strains 19 Romanian ecotypes were investigated. The ecotypes were collected from areas differentiated by anthropic utilization and environmental conditions. Even though populations of *D. melanogaster* are not really isolated it has been identified phenotypic and genotypic evident polymorphism. There are compared the quantitative and behavior traits.

Keywords: *Drosophila* ecotypes; behaviour; fertility, body size

Introduction

Concerns of knowledge and characterization of the ecotypes in Romania are few and sporadically were made (1; 2). In almost all works mutants or isogenic lines were used. In 1943 Radu in collaboration with Catsch and Kanellis (1943 and 1967) communicated the results of radiation on *Drosophila* lines (3). Tudose (1992) and Gavrilă (1996) used mutant genotypes of fruit fly as “model” for their studies. A tentative to collect and to characterize the Romanian *Drosophila* ecotypes was initiated on USAMVB Department of Genetics since 1984. Later in 2008 due to a research program (PNII - 52158 - TRICHOAS) the previous stock made Romanian ecotypes (5) and classical strains (5) were enriched with other 11 ecotypes.

For a cosmopolite organism as *Drosophila* the environment specificity is a frame in which it has to survive to adapt and to evolve or to extinct. The fruit fly physiological particularities are influenced by the environment changes and indicate its adaptability vs. vulnerability (4; 5; 6). The ability to colonize multiple sites is an indication of the biological success of many species as well as on *Drosophila*. For *Drosophila* usually the number of habitats within a geographical area is large. If there is a competition, however, it may be reduced by natural selection by means of adaptation in the available sites (7). In those new niches the fruit fly is obligated to adapt its phenotype and behavior to those specific conditions. This is the cause of the improved

¹ Banat University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine "Regele Mihai I al României", Timișoara, România [galliabutnaru@usab-tm.ro]

changes and if they are fixed are leading to the evolved populations of fruit flies (8).

In the fruit fly species the clinal variability was a subject of intense study (9, 10; 11, 12, 13). The *Drosophila* species exhibits high viability across a wide range of growth conditions. The limit of temperatures varies from 10 > 14°C to 28 > 33°C. Adult fertility is maintained across a somewhat narrower range (12 > 14°C to 28 > 30°C; 14). For aridity, individual maximum limits depend on the nature of the flies being 24h. The forms selected for desiccation (reduced humidity to 10%) survive only few hours (15). In some *Drosophila* species the limits might be modified by plastic responses (16, 17).

Previous studies on *Drosophila* species have shown that inherent morphology is highly species specific, and differs among ecotypes (e.g., tropical, continental, hilly, forest etc).

We expected to be a variation among and within Romanian ecotypes of *Drosophila* generated by the environmental peculiarities expressed in the heterogeneity of the morphological traits and individuals' behavior.

The population of fruit flies developed in the "anthropic" sites is made up of individual phenotypes perfectly adapted to the particular environment. In our case ecological site is defined as the larvae specific feeding conditions, the adults foraging, assortment of fruits, the space localization, weather conditions and radiation.

In this paper, we address the following questions: [1] how is the individual's behavioral response to different constraints conditions; [2] there are additional "events"?; [3] how is the population structure and the fertility of *Drosophila* ecotypes in the first generations after trapping?; [4] are body size particularities connected to sexual dimorphism and site of origin?.

The Experimental and Environmental Details

Generally, populations vary and constantly adapts to their environment: food, the seasonality, land forces, and other "constraints" factors. In order to characterize and highlight the existing differences among ecotypes it is necessary to know the specificity of local environment. This is the reason to give each developmental site description of *Drosophila* populations. In **Tab. 1** are indicated the locations and the number of ecotypes along with some environmental particularities.

The *Drosophila* clones were collected in different niche located in:

- **Alba, Arad and Timiș** Counties, situated in the Northern-Southern West part where the climate is more gentle, with Mediterranean influence, rainfall varying from 800mm, 590mm and 620mm respectively;

- **Dolj** and **Constanta** Counties situated in South and South East part of Romania with an arid climate and powerful tendencies of desertification; the average of precipitations are 630 and 450 mm respectively; and

- **Gorj** County surrounded by Southern Carpathians mountains has a moderate-continental climate and a weak Mediterranean influence. The annual average temperatures vary between 6-10°C and rainfall between 600-800 mm.

In the collection localities the environment is more or less different from the general pattern of the county. Their peculiarities are shown further.

From **Roşia Montana** (Alba County, 46°18'N and 23°08'/ 850-1000 MASL) 2 ecotypes were collected (**RM-North** and **RM-Church**). Roşia Montană is situated in the Apuseni Mountains in the Red Valley with gentle climate even if the 6.0°C temperature average is under favorable limits. The predominant soils are *Eutric Cambisols* and *Lepti eutric Cambisols* weakly acidic and acidic respectively. The area is surrounded by forests. The amount of rain is more than 900mm (**Tab.1**). Rosia Montana is famous for their gold mines, uranium, and other rare and heavy metals. The radioactivity of soil is higher than 1100 Bq/kg. Amount of 430 Bq/kg/fresh materials were detected in plants (**ANPM 2009**; 18). In leaves the concentration of heavy metals was higher than normal level (Ni, Pb, Cu, Zn; 19). The cultivated plants are vines, plums, apples, pears trees and in forest are plenty of berries. The environment and food for larva and adults fruit fly development was abundant but we presume being apart due to the heavy metals presence. Huge populations of fly were moving in gardens and orchards. To collect *Drosophila* was not a problem. We hope to identify tolerant genotypes for heavy metals and other stress conditions. In lab conditions only RM-Ch survived. The wild population was a mix made from normal and big individuals (**RM-n** and **RM-B**).

Socodor (Pedological Research Centre), **Nadab** and **Barzava** communes are located in **Arad** County. The Socodor and Nadab are situated on Solonetz basic and ultra basic pH >8.5 soils associated with flat lands in a climate with hot – dry summers. The rainfall varied from 430 to 590mm respectively. It is a farming and horticulture ecosystem. The main crops are corn, cabbage, tomatoes, plums, apples, and vines. In August in vineyards a lot of fruit flies are foraging. From Socodor and Nadab we collected 4 and 2 “ecotypes” respectively and finally due to small differences among them preserved only one mix sample for each location. We presume to identify tolerance to salt and heat genotypes.

The Barzava is a uranium mining locality where the radionuclides presence is higher than the admissible average concentration for our Country (**Tab.1**; Bq/Kg dm; **ANPM.ro**). It is surrounded by hills covered with forests. The *haplic luvisol* is very acid (pH – 5.13 – 6.2). The climate is continental - temperate with an average of temperatures 6 - 10°C and in summer shall be 18

-20°C. Precipitation ranges 600 to 800 mm. Plums, mirabelle, apples and different vegetables are the main cultivated plants. In the woods and glades are growing crab apples and cherries and dog roses. We collected an ecotype in the proximity of greened uranium mines (Barzava 11) and of the forest (Barzava Forest). In both places the amount of visiting fruit flies was small. It seems to be an unfavorable ecosystem for fruit fly.

Timisoara and **Sag of Timiș** are located in southeastern Pannonian Plain. For the temperate continental climate of Timisoara the main characteristic consists in diversity and irregularities of atmospheric processes. Warm air masses blowing from the Adriatic Sea and Atlantic Ocean are bringing a lot of rain. In the spring and summer the temperatures are terrible. The polar – continental air coming from East, from the beginning of September, is temperate by Mediterranean cyclones. The average annual temperature and rains are 10.6°C and 629mm respectively. Even that the desertification process is visible. In “Timisoara” point of collection the presence of radionuclides is varying from low (Ra-226) to high (Ac-228 [Th-232] and K-40; **Tab.1**). Around Timisoara a strong agricultural, horticultural vineyards and fruit growing area are. For *Drosophila* the stress of climatic conditions is moderated by excess of food. From June the fruit fly is omnipresent. Since 2008 and 2009 Timisoara and Sag ecotypes are preserved.

The **Giubega** (43°98' N – 44°05'E), **Motatei** (23°61' N – 23°77'E) and **Bucovat/Palilula** (44°17' N – 23°43'E) are situated in the South part of Dolj County. This is the hottest and driest area from Ro. Generally is a plain land (30 – 35m MASL) only Palilula is in gentle hilly – wooded ecosystem (350m MASL). For Giubega and Motatei generally the climate is continental with weak Mediterranean influence but both localities are situated in proximity of sandy soils of the “Dolj desert”. In the summer the temperatures are extremely high. +10.5°C is the average of annual temperature associated with 610mm/year precipitations not uniformly distributed. The radionuclides concentration is higher than minimum admissible for Romania. Even if the Bucovat/Palilula is considerate having a high amount of radiation the radionuclides presence in the point of collection was low (**Tab.1**). In the 3 ecotypes collected in Dolj areas we hope to identify tolerant genotypes for desiccation and resistant to high temperature and radiation (20).

Tab. 1 General description of the environment in which *Drosophila* ecotypes have evolved

no.	Ecotype	Country	Ecosystem	Altitude mMASL	Latitude N	Longitude E	Soil	Rain (mm) Humid (%)	T°C	Radionuclides	
										¹⁾ Natural	²⁾ Artificial
1	Oregon [R]		Lab conditions CONTROL	90			Standard culture medium	70 – 80 %	22	Addm. limits m	X Max
2	White [w ¹¹¹³]								-	Ra-226	14.04
3	Ebony [e]	TM		90	45°45'	21°13'			25	Ac-228	4.65
4	Timisoara		Agriculture Horticulture.	90			Cambic- chernozem	629 mm	10.6	K-40	104.60
5	Sag*			85	45°39'	21°10'		584 mm	10.9	30.5<X; 42.5>X; 650>Max	
6	Socodor		Agriculture Horticulture	94	46°31'	21°26'	Solonetz pH>8.5	430 mm	10.4	29.9<X; 36.7>X; 609>X	
7	Nadab	AR		89	46°29'	21°31'		590 mm		962.1>Max; 47.2>X; 421>X	
8	Barzava** 11		Horticulture Agriculture Forest	200	46°07'	21°59'	Haplic luvisol pH = 5.7	720 mm	8.2	43.6>X; 45.9>X; 540>X	
9	Barzava** Forest			210	46°07'	21°59'				Soil radioactivity> 1100Bq/kg	
10	Roşia Montana n**	AB	Horticulture	930	46°18'	23°07'	Cambisols	900 mm	6		
11	Roşia Montana B**										
12	Bucovat***		Forest Horticulture.	130	44°16'	23°42'	Preluvosol	638 mm	10	15.5<X; 30.6>X; 291<X	
13	Grubea	DJ	Agriculture Horticulture	81	44°07'	23°25'	Reddish eutricambosol	570 mm	10.5	23.5<X; 28.6<X; 371<X	
14	Motatet			69	44°05'	23°12'					
15	Târgu Jiu City		Urban/Horti.	205	45°03'	23°17'	Preluvosol; reddish subtype	620 mm	9.7		
16	Peşteana			215	44°51'	23°18'					
17	Rovinari****	GJ	Horticulture (submontane)	201	44°54'	23°10'		600 mm	10	26.5<X; 25.3<X; 375<X 35.5>X; 43.9<X; 586>X	
18	Urdari			146	44°47'	23°17'					
19	Ploporu Grey										
20	Ploporu Black n		Cellar for fruit fermentation	140	44°47'	23°21'	Preluvosol moderate acid	550 mm	10	23.5<X; 31.8>X; 504>X	
21	Ploporu Black B										
22	Cernavoda	CT	Fruit market	50	44°37'	28°08'	Kastanozem mildly alkaline	450 mm	11	30.1<X; 32.2>Max; 430<X	

* ecosystem anthropic modified; * thermal plant; ** mining activity; *** high natural radioactivity; **** mining activity and power plant

MASL: Meters above sea level;

¹⁾ Natural Radionuclide Ra-226; Ac-228; K-40 Bq/kg soil 0-40cm; ²⁾ Artificial Radionuclides Cs-137 Chernobyl;

#, X, Max represents the minimum, average and maximum radionuclides limits a drilled in Romania;

Maximum average / Country

n =normal; B = big individual

More than a quarter of ecotypes were collected from **Gorj County**. It is an interesting area for its anthropic modified environment and a particular climate. Widely used is coal mining and power plant business. A special attention was given to human life and health monitoring (18). The soil analysis pointed out the amount of natural radionuclides Ra-226, Ac-228 and K-40 being between minimum and medium admissible in Romania. In comparison to Urdari and Plopsoru in the Rovinari area the natural and artificial radioactivity is low. The highest artificial radioactivity generated by Cs-137 was in Plopsoru. Due to large fields of orchards the environment is proper for fruit fly. Outside or in the basement the moist and warm environment was provided by plums, mirabelle, apples and grapes in fermentation. We presume an special activation of gene complex in survived individuals providing them a better suitability to the environment conditions noticeable in phenotype. Plopsoru Black sustains our presumption.

Cernavoda (Constanta County) is one of the warmest cities in Romania. There is moderate subtropical climate with maritime and some continental influences. In summer the days and nights are very warm and dry. In autumn the days can be warmer than June. Winter can be very windy and cool. Winter arrives much later than in other Counties weather is mild with 8°C to 12°C. The large area of vineyards, orchard and vegetable gardens represents a “paradise” for *Drosophila*. From Cernavoda area 2 “ecotypes” were collected from fruit market and cellar of grapes fermentation. Only Cernavoda (fruit market) was used in present work.

Some events in the collecting work have generated a lot of questions yet unresolved. These are the Plopsoru Black ecotype and the "big" individuals collected from Rosia Montana and Plopsoru.

Materials and Methods

19 wild *Drosophila* ecotypes were compared with Oregon (R), White 1118 (w¹¹¹⁸) and Ebony (e) stock strains. Flies were raised in glass vials on standard medium at 25/22°C. Throughout this work the ecotypes are always designated with the place name of collection. For each question under investigation the method of working is presented.

Statistic work: Using two-factor analysis of variance has been possible to establish the hierarchy among ecotypes dependent of their average size. The sexual dimorphism was determinate and the size difference between male and female individuals was evaluated. Averages were compared using Least Difference test (LD) (21). The significance of differences was expressed based on alphabetic symbols, being considered as significant (at $p < 0.05$; A>B>C>D>E).

Results and Discussions

The primary screening followed wild fruit fly collected from natural conditions in September on gardens, basements, forest from different localities and from minimum 5 points (replications). The wild adults were caught in 800cmc glass vials containing bananas in fermentation and “*Drosophila* standard medium”.

To prevent the constraints effects as well as the reduce space, inbreeding effect and the new diet 10:10 outdoor adults were the “starter” of a new generation. The “*in situ*” parents have lay eggs during five days, after which they have been eliminated. The hatched individuals formed the first “*ex situ*” generation (G1) further preserved in laboratory conditions. Each generation has been initiated from a couple of 10♀:10♂; maintained at a size of at least 100 individuals.

The final result consists in a collection of ecotypes that have a high probability of phenotypic and behavioral similarity. In Plopsoru village in the same place two forms were captured.

In the first part of work the G1 and G2 generations were evaluated (**Tab.2**).

To understand the phenotype and behavior difference of flies, grown in outdoor and in limited space (jars) the adult’s fertility body and wings sizes were evaluated in G1 and G2. The viability, the motility, and the inbreeding effect were also assessed.

After the fly capture, in the lab conditions the population size stability was followed. On 50 of adults the body size was evaluated. Daily the emerged adults male and female were counted. Finally the evolution of population growth/day and total amount of adults were established (**Tab.2**).

Tab. 2. The fertility of *Drosophila* individuals originating from *in situ* (natural conditions) and *ex situ* (laboratory conditions) estimated by the size of progeny formed in the first generation of (G1) and the second (G2) [10♀: 10♂]

no.	Ecotypes The size and population structure	The first generation after trapping (G1)			The grown generation in lab. conditions (G2)			The % decrease of fertility in G2		
		Total	♀	♂	Total	♀	♂	Total	♀	♂
1	Oregon [R]	-	-	-	116 ± 39.8	61	55	-	-	-
2	White [w ¹¹¹⁸]	-	-	-	104 ± 22.3	48	56	-	-	-
3	Ebony [e]	-	-	-	173 ± 15.9	80	93	-	-	-
4	Timisoara [North]	498 ± 7.5	238	260	416 ± 3.6	210	206	83.53	88.24	79.23
5	Sag* [Timis]	232 ± 9.2	106	116	186 ± 12.0	100	86	80.17	94.34	74.14
6	Socodor	423 ± 28.0	203	220	324 ± 16.1	161	163	76.59	78.31	74.09
7	Nadab	448 ± 14.5	198	250	403 ± 8.7	206	200	89.95	97.53	80.00
8	Barzava** 11	206 ± 16.8	100	106	84 ± 21.1	39	45	40.78	39.00	42.45
9	Barzava forest**	116 ± 12.8	49	67	76 ± 5.6	33	43	65.52	67.45	64.18
10	Rosia Montana** Normal [n]	519 ± 4.0	248	271	134 ± 5.3	73	61	25.82	29.44	22.51
11	Rosia Montana** Big [B]	84 ± 19.0	41	43	18 ± 15.2	10	8	21.43	24.39	18.60
12	Bucovat***	378 ± 59.0	183	195	178 ± 16.0	87	101	47.09	47.54	51.78
13	Giubega	364 ± 3.6	173	198	218 ± 4.8	110	108	59.89	63.58	54.55
14	Motatei	336 ± 2.5	158	178	241 ± 3.1	119	122	71.73	75.32	68.54
15	Targu Jiu [City]	346 ± 2.5	166	180	204 ± 3.7	104	100	58.96	62.65	55.56
16	Pestana	445 ± 19.0	221	224	268 ± 9.4	129	139	60.22	58.37	62.05
17	Turceni****	233 ± 13.0	115	118	200 ± 14.5	102	98	85.84	88.69	83.05
18	Urdari	315 ± 5.2	152	163	244 ± 4.8	120	124	77.46	78.94	76.07
19	Ploporu Gray	253 ± 16.0	112	141	213 ± 17.8	101	112	84.19	90.18	79.43
20	Ploporu Black Normal [n]	26 ± 18.3	8	18	59 ± 17.9	21	38	226.92	262.50	211.11
21	Ploporu Black Big [B]	15 ± 24.1	6	9	21 ± 58.0	9	12	140.00	150.00	133.3
22	Cernavoda	324 ± 3.1	161	163	116 ± 5.2	55	61	35.80	34.16	37.42
	$\bar{x} \pm s_x$	339.8 ± 27.1	161.4 ± 13.2	178.1 ± 14.2	219.1 ± 23.9	109.3 ± 12.3	110.6 ± 11.8	120.7 ± 52.1	52.1 ± 25.5	67.6 ± 70.0
	% of male and female in population	100	47.54	52.46	100	49.90	50.10			

1. The *Drosophila* behavior during collection and accommodation to laboratory conditions

Only a small part of individuals “preferred” to use standard or banana food. The flies visited the vials but did not “enjoy” the medium used for capture. A mixture of banana and grapes was the proper food for adults to laying eggs. The traps with standard medium were useful only in unfavorable conditions and for a long time for capture. Even if there is a large genetic variation for food-related traits (22) the analyzed wild ecotypes exhibited a selective response. It seems that at Romanian wild ecotypes the gustatory perception was selected for specific food. Ueno et al 2001 (23) demonstrated that the gustatory phenotype modification took place when a single-nucleotide in *Gr5a* gene was changed. Only Ala218Thr DNP occurs naturally in the *Gr5a* gene polymorphism. The gustatory behavior is still under investigation (24).

After capturing the adults were extremely anxious. Duration to adapt to the limited space varied a few days and for some genotypes never. After a Brownian movement they rested on the plug (the upper part of jar) and then went down to the culture medium. In this period of "orientation" many individuals did not survived. The fly lethality could be caused by the limited space, anxiety, and reproductive constraints (inbreeding).

2. Apart events notification

An unusual situation appeared at Rosia Montana and Plopsoru ecotypes. The natural populations were a mixture of normal and big individuals. In the Plopsoru population were observed grey and among they a few black individuals

The big individuals were separated from the normal form and mated apart.

They survived only for a few generations. During this time the population size continually decreased and finally disappeared.

We wanted to establish the phenotypic difference between normal and big individuals; between female and male; and ecotypes, Rosia Montana and Plopsoru Black originated in two different Counties. The statistical work pointed out significant differences between big and normal individuals and female and male averages [$LSD_{1\%} < d = 0.68$ and $< d = 0.726$ mm respectively]. It was an insignificant difference between Rosia Montana and Plopsoru Black ecotypes [$LSD_{5\%} > d = 0.048$]. We presume that the big individuals appeared in very large populations and are the result of larval **particular/over** food.

The *ex situ* conditions favored the Plopsoru Black individuals (**Tab.2**). With each generation the population was larger. Our observations pointed out their particularities. They are black with an evident sexual dimorphism. The eggs bear 6-9 appendages. The life cycle is long (23-25 days at 25°C; 25). It is a philo-darkness form very sensitive to inbreeding. The Plopsoru Black formed a particular strain. Up to now its taxonomic position was not clarified. Accidentally

in the large populations big individuals emerged. It was the reason to suppose that in large population it is possible to appear and survive big individuals. In case of Plopsoru ecotypes we supposed the action of disruptive selection. The first result was the population divergence in grey and black. The polymorphism created two subpopulations with completely different traits which finally were sexual isolated

3. The fertility evolution of *Drosophila* ecotypes

The shift from a "free" environment evolution to laboratory constraints growing conditions is a major stress for all individuals. The fertility is the most sensitive reply of organism pointing out its homeostasis. It was comparatively assessed the fertility of individuals coming from the natural environment with those formed in laboratory conditions. The determination was made through the number of new emerged progeny (**Tab.2**). The G1 populations emerged from *in situ* parents with a high fertility. In G1 the offspring growth varied from 116 ± 12.8 to 519 ± 4.0 on Barzava Forest and Rosia Montana respectively. Almost all ecotypes were similar as fertility ($\bar{x} \pm s_x = 339.8 \pm 27.1$). In the second generation (G2) the fertility dropped down from 76 ± 5.6 to 416 ± 3.6 at Barzava Forest and Timisoara respectively. Generally the fertility of "*ex situ*" parents was diminished ($\bar{x} \pm s_x = 219.1 \pm 23.9$). In the both generations the average of male individuals was higher than that of female ($178.1 \pm 14.2 > 161.4 \pm 13.2$ and $110.6 \pm 11.8 > 109.3 \pm 12.3$). In G2 the sex ratio was close to normal (1:1). For all of the followed ecotypes the body size decreased with larval density.

Our results are in concordance with other studies. **Billeter** et al., (2012; 26) mentioned that the changes in "social context" had dramatic effects on reproductive success. The observations emphasized the Rosia Montana, Bazava and Bucovat ecotypes homeostasis. The ecotypes evolved in radioactive hilly environment and their transfer in lab conditions strongly influenced the G2 fertility. **Messina** (1991; 27) emphasized "even in the absence of plasticity, in a spatially distributed population in a uniform environment there is always some positive selection on dispersal rate due to local kin competition" It is known that changes in temperature almost always affect vital parameters of *Drosophila* populations such as viability, fertility, development time and other factors that influence the rate of population growth and survival (28)

4. The Body Size in Ecotypes and Sexual Dimorphism

Body size is a major fitness-related that contributes to adaptation successful. The body size of *Drosophila* natural populations in relation with different environmental factors was a subject of studies (29).

In our case the large trait variability among ecotypes imposes to establish the differences among ecotypes and its significance. 25 males and 25 female was the

subject of measurement. Only Plopsoru Black made an exception. The results of statistical analysis are shown in **Tab. 3**.

Tab.3. Variance Analysis for the involvement of male and female body size and the ecotype upon the average size of Romanian *Drosophila* "landraces"

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F	Probability
Repetitions	0.696	2	0.348	3.74	
body growth of male and female [A]	12.243	1	12.243	131.71**	0.008
Residual [A]	0.186	2	0.093	1.25	
Landraces [B]	18.092	21	0.862	11.56**	<.001
Individuals x Landraces	1.197	21	0.057	0.77	0.752
Residual [B]	6.258	84	0.075		
Total	38.672	131			

A - sex of individuals: a¹- female and a²- male

B -genotypes [19 landraces and 3 strains]

The analysis of variance [**Tab 3**] reveals the significant differences [**] between individuals [males/females] and among ecotypes.

The hierarchical analysis of variance outlined in **Tab. 4** illustrates the differences of general body size of adults and the trait similitude between females and males.

Tab. 4 The involvement of individual female and male size on the general habitus of *Drosophila* population originated in various environmental sites

no	no.of Eco.	Landraces	♀&♂ individuals size [mm]				The general size [mm]			
			Female	signif	Male	signif	$\bar{x} \pm s_x$	signif	S%	
1	20	Plopsoru Black [B]	x 4.60	a	y 3.83	a	4.22±0.23	A	13.45	
2	10	Rosia Montana [B]	4.30	ab	3.77	a	4.03±0.14	AB	8.68	
3	18	Urdari	x 4.07b	b	y 3.50	ab	3.78±0.22	B	14.52	
4	9	Sag	x 3.70	bc	y 3.10	bc	3.40±0.15	C	11.00	
5	8	Timisoara North	x 3.70	bc	y 3.07	bc	3.38±0.16	C	11.43	
6	3	Ebony [e]	x 3.70	bc	y 3.03	cd	3.37±0.16	C	11.38	
7	19	Plopsoru Grey	x 3.70	bc	y 2.97	cd	3.33±0.17	CD	12.82	
8	4	Socodor	x 3.63	c	y 2.97	cd	3.30±0.16	CDE	11.97	
9	11	Rosia Montana [n]	x 3.50	cd	x 3.10	bc	3.30±0.09	CDE	6.91	
10	6	Barzava 11	x 3.50	cd	y 2.93	cde	3.22±0.13	CDEF	9.91	
11	21	Plopsoru Black [n]	x 3.50	cd	y 2.77	cdef	3.13±0.21	CDEFG	16.96	
12	7	Barzava Forest	x 3.30	cdef	x 2.93	cde	3.12±0.10	CDEFG	10.70	
13	17	Turceni	x 3.37	cde	x 2.70	cdef	3.03±0.16	DEFG	12.97	
14	13	Giubega	x 3.27	cdef	y 2.77	cdef	3.02±0.13	EFG	10.36	
15	1	Oregon [R]	x 3.47	cd	y 2.53	ef	3.00±0.24	EFG	20.00	
16	5	Nadab	x 3.30	cdef	y 2.60	def	2.95±0.20	FGH	16.71	

17	15	Targu Jiu [City]	x 3.13	def	x 2.77	cdef	2.95±0.16	FGH	13.00
18	16	Pesteană	x 3.27	cdef	x 2.63	def	2.95±0.19	FGH	15.72
19	12	Bucovat	x 3.33	cdef	y 2.53	ef	2.93±0.20	FGH	16.79
20	22	Cernavoda	x 2.97	ef	x 2.87	cde	2.92±0.18	FGH	15.09
21	14	Motatei	x 3.37	cde	y 2.40	f	2.88±0.24	GH	20.51
22	2	White 1118 [w ¹¹¹⁸]	x 2.93	f	y 2.43	f	2.68±0.14	H	12.78
23		$\bar{x} \pm s_x$	3.53±0.06		2.92±0.05		3.22±0.05		
24		CV%	12.97		15.22		16.86		

-Individuals - LSD_{5%} = 0.23 mm LSD_{1%} = 0.53 mm LSD_{0,1%} = 1.68 mm (X,Y,Z)

-Landraces - LSD_{5%} = 0.31 mm LSD_{1%} = 0.41 mm LSD_{0,1%} = 0.54 mm (A,B,C)

-Individuals x Landraces - LSD_{5%} = 0.46mm LSD_{1%} = 0.59 mm LSD_{0,1%} = 0.77 mm (x, y, z)

-Landraces x Individuals- LSD_{5%} = 0.44 mm LSD_{1%} = 0.59 mm LSD_{0,1%} = 0.76 mm (a, b, c)

On all ecotypes the body size of females was larger compared with the males (3.53±0.06>2.92±0.05). The body size varied from 2.93 to 4.07mm on female and 2.46 to 3.50mm on males. The results of variance analysis indicated that only 36.4% and 45.6% female and male ecotypes pointed out a larger body size than the overall body size average/sex (3.53±0.06mm and 2.92±0.05mm). The analyzed ecotypes showed moderate variability in terms of body size in females and males of *Drosophila* [10 <CV%> 20]. It was found that for more than a quarter of the examined ecotypes the overall effects for both sexes were small and without significance (x / x). Their similarity or insignificant sexual dimorphism appears to be caused by hilly forests and orchards environment, a limited possibilities of movement, associated with low temperatures. However, the body size among individuals in certain specific physical environments was large and significant (**Tab. 4**). It was concluded that knowledge of quantitative trait, in our case the body size, is directly associated with fitness for fertility. An exception was Rosia Montana Big.

Other similar studies on body weight pointed out the effect of disruptive selection only in assortative mating (without complete sexual isolation between the subpopulations). These experiments demonstrated that developmental temperatures, both within and between generations, influence territorial success of flies (30).

Conclusions

The Romanian studied ecotypes emphasized a large variability in quantitative traits as well as fertility and body size.

Even if the fruit fly populations are not real isolated it has been identified interpopulational and intrapopulational phenotypic polymorphism.

The presence of two forms of *Drosophila* in the same niche [Plopsoru] pointed out their commune origin separated due to disruptive selection.

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RESTORING IN LANDSCAPE (GARDEN) ARCHITECTURE APPLICATION: THE BOULEVARD GENERAL PAVEL KISELEFF.

Dan ȘCHIOPU¹, Antonia IVAȘCU¹

Keywords: garden architecture, landscape architecture, niche, restoration, Paul Kiseleff road.

Among pleasant places in Bucharest, can be counted also the Boulevard General Pavel Kiseleff. It was promenades on horseback area, place where they were going beats with flowers, then, after the second world war, it was preferred for walks his bike. Now on our days, bus called "Bucharest City Tour" has included in its routing tour also this emblematic street of Bucharest.

Fig. 1. Bus "Bucharest City Tour" included in the route and the Boulevard General Pavel Kiseleff

In the year 2011, the French journalist Audrey Favin (quoted by I. L. Popescu (2013) shows that, from an analysis of the company's market as the "Euromonitor", "Bucharest is the 55-th the most visited city in the world by foreign tourists, before some towns such as Milan, Venice, Florence (located on the sites 65.78 and 79) or Lisbon."

Continuing the highway Bucharest, Ploiesti, the Boulevard General Pavel Kiseleff constitutes a passage connecting periurban space, Baneasa forest - with one in the urban areas, the Herastrau Park., then, also with the Park Kiseleff. (Figure 2)

¹ Academy of Romanian Scientists

Fig. 2 - A. Continuing the Highway Bucharest, Ploiesti, the Boulevard General Pavel Kiseleff constitutes a passage connecting periurban space, Baneasa forest - with one in the urban areas, the Herastrau Park., the Arch of Triumph, up to Str. Ion Mincu Architect, then see Fig. 2 -B.

Fig. 2-B. Continuation of fig. 2-A, from Str. Ion Mincu Architect, by Kiseleff Park, up to Victoria Square and on Unirii Avenue Lascar until Romana Square.

From Piața Presei up to the Arch of Triumph, the Boulevard has three lanes - side two, each with three bands in only one direction, and, in the middle, with two lanes in each direction. These roadways are separated through spaces planted with a row of trees, (fig. 3), which determines, in addition to a safe fluency of vehicle traffic, also a very good air circulation. The road is lined by a strip with trees and shrubs, which separate it from the Sports Complex "Iolanda Balas-Söter" - on the right-hand side (seen in the Arch of Triumph direction) - and by the Village Museum of "Dimitrie Gusti" (on the left-hand side). These strips are delimited to pavements of a hedge hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.)

Fig. 3. Boulevard Pavel Kiseleff from "Piata preseii" up to the Arch of Triumph, has three lanes separated through spaces planted with a row of trees, (photo original)

From the Square of the Arch of Triumph, remain only four lanes, up from the Street Architect Ion Mincu. This portion has buildings surrounded by wide-open spaces, with rich vegetation- trees and bushes, which facilitates atmospheric currents. From the Street Architect Ion Mincu it links with Kiseleff Park, which it crosses up to the Museum of Geology – to Victoria Square. (Fig.2). Then, from Victoria Square up in the Romana Square, by the Avenue Lascar Catargiu, ensures good ventilation of the city, while maintaining a microclimate very comfortable and hygienic.

The Boulevard Pavel Kiseleff is thus a corridor linking green areas arranged "in spots" (areas isolated in different areas of localities) transforming "in the network" the system of green spaces, with all the advantages coming from here: good ventilation and the ability of wildlife to move wider areas. "As an "emotional" (as man) we can feel the need of isolation or, sometimes, approach for our fellow human beings; as an "emotional" the man looking for harmony, the landscape unity, that we're calling „beauty”.

All these must be taken into account in the design of green spaces (landscapes), in order to determine optimal conditions for each activity, for each "status", for the idea that green spaces can awaken and stimulate in the visitor feeling of a "real life". (O. Simonds quoted by Negrutiu Filofteia, 1980, p. 56-57).

„Parks need to be raised up to the level of cultural museums, constituting, together with them, a national valuable treasure. In any case, parks must not be created after a template, but must have their local individuality, their specific differences which characterize appropriate population and the territory where they are located." (Carmazinu Cacovschi V. , 1978, p. 112).

For this reason, we believe that, as well as any work of art, also parks and green spaces, as a general rule - when portions of them got damaged, must be

restored, brought to their original appearance, keeping them in such aesthetic and functional value they had before.

In generally, the ecological importance adds aesthetic value to this important traffic way.

To our regret, in the past few years, the aesthetics value of the portion between Piata Presei and the Arch of Triumph was affected by different works that we consider to be unsatisfactory.

Material and method

As material and we have used photographs taken in 2006 and I compared the situation with these images.

Results and discussion

In fig. 4, It is to be noted that hedge hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L) ., had some niches, in which they were located banks. The hornbeam can help to ensure the height required to that slots to provide isolation from the rest of the space.

Fig. 4. Niche with a bank, on the Boulevard Pavel Kiseleff, in the year 2006 (photo original)

The hedge become an old one, that in many places can barely recognized its existence, and niches are gone in majority or can barely been identify (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Niches in which they were located banks can barely be identify

Banks were replaced by new ones, which are placed on the sidewalk outside former niches (fig. 6), so that "the need for isolation can no longer be satisfied".

In addition, these banks can be seen along its entire length road, and casual "tired people", which slept on them, are exposed to sight and we don't think that their image makes a good impression for visitors - foreign and Romanian ones - in the buses which called "Bucharest City Tour".

Fig. 6. Banks have been placed on the sidewalk outside former niches.

We believe that, as well as any work of art, and parks must be restored, it means brought to their original appearance, keeping them in such aesthetic and functional value they had previously.

In addition, these banks can be seen along its entire length road, and casual "tired walkers", which sleep on them, are exposed to sight and we don't think that their image makes a good impression for visitors - foreign and Romanian one - in the buses which are "Bucharest City Tour"

Fig. 7. Prospective „tired walkers” which sleep or are resting on the benches, are exposed to all vision along the road

Conclusions

Of those reported, results following conclusions:

1. Green areas bordering the Boulevard Pavel Kisaeleff on the portion of Piata Presei and Arch of Triumph must be restored, keeping them the initial aesthetic and functional destination.
2. Hedge it is necessary to be replanted, holding the niches in which they were located banks.
3. To the restored of the hedge must be used the same specie - hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.) which offer the degree of required isolation.
4. It is essential that banks be repositioned into the niches, as they were originally.

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PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION OF MILK IN ROMANIA. CURRENT LEVELS AND MARKET TRENDS

Elena STOIAN¹, Marian CONSTANTIN²,
Ioan Iulian ALECU³, Andreea Raluca CONSTANTIN⁴

Abstract. This paper aims at underlying a set of trends within the market chain of milk and milk derivatives, at national level in the period 2007-2012, on the data available within the National Institute of Statistics. The analysis highlights the following: the trend of milk production increase, simultaneously with the available production levels and the target to industrial transformation, which shows a decrease of the consumption availability. Foreign trade is characterized by an increase while the import records a higher pace than exports.

Keywords: available production, production potential, resources/uses, domestic consumption availability, industrial processing, foreign trade (import/export), average annual gross/net consumption, calories/categories of nutrient factors (proteins, glucides and lipids).

1. Introduction

This paper aims to emphasize the production and consumption trends in dairy products/ milk derivatives, which display significant variations at national level.

The use of synthetic markers and derivatives, present in the period 2007-2012 annual structure, the description of the levels of these markers, supplemented by appropriate comparative forms highlights the following: the trend of milk production increase, simultaneously with the available production levels and the target to industrial transformation, which shows a decrease of the consumption availability; foreign trade is characterized by an increase while the import records a higher pace than exports; average annual and daily food consumption shows variations and a

¹Title: Prof., PhD, Faculty of Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania (e-mail: stoian_ie@yahoo.com).

²Prof., PhD, Faculty of Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania(e-mail: marianconstantin2014@yahoo.com).

³Lecturer, PhD, Faculty of Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania (e-mail: iulian_alecu2000@yahoo.com).

⁴PhD, Faculty of Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania (e-mail: andreearconstantin@gmail.com).

decreasing rate. Analysis of the evolutionary form: production→use→consumption which aims at the correction/ alignment to the evolutionary system of the EU chain.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper aims at underlying a set of trends within the market chain of milk and milk derivatives. The approach to this problem required the use of some specific markers (synthetic and derivatives) that bring to the fore and present the problems specific to the market chain at national level in the period 2007-2012. The computation basis consisted of the data available within the National Institute of Statistics, by means of which the quantitative representation of the values for milk/ dairy derivatives was equated with 3.5% fat milk. Highlighting the level of the markers was performed on the basis of processing and interpreting the most recent data and information, establishing the result of a mainly statistical market research. [2, 3]

The research started from the presence of annual differences for milk which were based on an evolutionary form production→use→consumption. In the methodology employed, based on their contents, the database focused on¹: medium consumption (the value of the goods and services which are either processed, or entirely consumed during the production process); available production (the quantities of primary products obtained during the reference period, including the quantities used by the producers from their own production, self-consumption, and/or the quantities of processed products, excluding the waste of the production process); domestic consumption availabilities (the quantities of food products available for the domestic consumption adjusted to the stocks variation), of which the available human consumption (the quantities of food products available for use in the population's food consumption during the reference period, both as primary products and as processed products, irrespective of the supply source); foreign trade (import/export); industrial processing (the quantities of products used in the industry in order to obtain a food derivative and for which a food balance is established separately from the primary product balance).

Methodologically, synthetic and derivative markers were expressed at quantitative and percentage level and the annual levels were monitored by means of comparative forms in the sequence of years. The comparative forms were expressed at the level of 2007, the sequence of years and the period average. [5]

Within this paper the following statistical markers were used: arithmetic mean, standard deviation, variance inflation factor and the statistical representation of these markers.

The formulas used for the calculus of these markers are presented hereafter [1, 2]:

For arithmetic mean:

¹Definitions according to Food and Agriculture Organization and Eurostat methodology, presented in Food Balances, National Institute of Statistics, 2008-2013

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum xi}{n} \quad (1)$$

where:

n = the number of years taken into consideration

For the annual average rate of growth [3, 4]:

$$r_{2007-2012} = [\prod (p_1 / p_0) / (n - 1)]^{(1/n)} \quad (2)$$

where:

$r_{2007-2012}$ = annual average rate of growth; $\prod (p_1/p_0)$ = markers for chain-linked growth

For standard deviation:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (\bar{x} - xi)^2}{n - 1}} \quad (3)$$

where:

M = standard deviation;

xi = the values of the average productions per a number of years;

n = the number of years taken into consideration

For the variance inflation factor:

$$C = \frac{\delta}{\bar{X}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where:

C = variance inflation factor (expressed in percentages)

The variance inflation factor can be: between 0-10% - low variation; between 10-20% - medium variation; over 20% - high variation.

The analysis of the comparative levels of supplementary consumptions was enhanced by the markers for the annual and daily total consumption levels. By means of the used markers, we observed the qualitative changes of the food consumption model, with particular references to knowing the quantities of the nutrient principles of the diet and, within this diet, of the proteins of animal origin.

By means of the methodological approach, we investigated the various forms of interpretation, by knowing the factors, with reference to their structure and trends.

3. Results and Discussion

The approach to the problem was structured tridimensionally as follows: production potential, medium consumption and foreign trade, food consumption, and their comparative level, respectively.

3.1. The potential of milk production and consumption availability

The volume of milk production is inseparably connected to the actual number of bovines, with particular reference to the categories of cows, buffalo cows and heifers. At organizational level, the volume of raw milk quantities taken over from the milk processing centers is in close correlation with the productions at the level of farms or the dairy primary production businesses. This raises questions about knowing the production potential expressed by means of the actual number of animals producing milk in Romania. The structure was rendered through the values of the markers presented in Table 1, emphasizing the aspects resulting from both the actual total and the number of animals per 100 ha, the annual level and the comparisons pointing up the following:

Table 1. Production potential for milk production in Romania
(actual number of cows, buffalo cows and heifers) [4, 5, 6]

<i>Specification</i>	<i>UM.</i>	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	<i>Average/ pace</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Variance inflation factor (%)</i>
Actual total of cows, buffalo cows and heifers	number thousands	1732	1639	1569	1299	1266	1265	1461.7	209.5	14.3
	in regard to previous year	-	0.95	0.96	0.83	0.97	1.00	-6.09	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	94.63	90.58	75	73.09	73.03	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	118.49	112.13	107.34	88.87	86.61	86.54	x	x	x
Number of animals (cows, buffalo cows and heifers) per 100 ha. of land	number	21.4	20.4	19.1	14.6	14.7	14.8	17.5	3.2	18.0
	% in regard to previous year	-	0.95	0.94	0.76	1.01	1.01	-7.11	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	98.61	94	88.01	67.28	67.74	68.2	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	122.28	116.57	109.14	83.42	84	84.57	x	x	x

- the analyzed dynamics point up an annual variation, the annual milk productions being in a decreasing trend. This situation is significant on the basis of the comparison between 2007 and the period average, that the minimum level of the last year, 2012, is 73.03% and 86.54%, respectively.

- a comparison with the number of animals (with reference to the categories of cows, buffalo cows and heifers) per 100 ha. points up the same regress, the minimum levels being of 67.28% in 2010 compared to 2007, and 84.00% in 2012 in regard to the period average;

- in regard to the average pace, we can observe negative values (-6.09 and -7.11), that the variance inflation shows a medium variation (10-20%), the fluctuations being of 14.3 from the actual number of cows, buffalo cows and heifers and of 16.0 from the number of animals (cows, buffalo cows and heifers) per 100 ha. of land.

We can notice that the production potential displays a decreasing trend, which is going to have consequences on the volume of obtained production. Thus, the volume of the quantities of milk products obtained in the processing units is characterized by the variation of its level along the years of the analyzed dynamics, to which we added the quantities of received raw milk which are not always determined. This is due to the fact that there is a tight correlation between the production level of the farms or dairy primary production businesses and the actual record system that they practice (references can be mainly made to the shortcomings of the records and the self-consumption of the milk productions).

In time, the dynamics of the available milk production, the uses, the domestic consumption availabilities and the human consumption availabilities, represented in Table 2, point up the following annual levels:

Table 2. Available production and consumption availability for milk in Romania [5, 6]

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	Average/ pace	Standard deviation	Variance inflation factor (%)
Available production	thousands of hl.	65373	64923	62195	55434	56201	54638	59794.0	4933.6	8.3
	in regard to previous year	-	0.99	0.96	0.89	1.01	0.97	-3.69	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	99.31	95.13	84.79	85.96	83.57	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	109.33	108.57	104.01	92.7	93.99	91.37	x	x	x
Uses	Thousands of hl.	67904	68304	66634	59759	61270	59415	63881.0	4173.2	6.5
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.98	0.9	1.03	0.97	-2.30	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	100.58	98.12	88	90.23	87.49	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	106.29	106.92	104.31	93.54	95.91	93	x	x	x

Domestic consumption availability	thousands of hl.	67563	67883	65988	58875	60340	58241	63148.3	4476.6	7.1
	in regard to previous year	-	1	0.97	0.89	1.02	0.97	-3.10	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	100.47	97.66	87.14	89.3	86.2	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	106.99	107.49	104.49	93.23	95.55	92.22	x	x	x
Human consumption availability	thousands of hl.	54445	54761	50063	47998	48616	46952	50472.5	3355.7	6.6
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.91	0.96	1.01	0.97	-2.87	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	100.58	91.95	88.15	89.29	86.23	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.87	108.49	99.18	95.09	96.32	93.02	x	x	x

- the available production records annual decreases as follows, in 2012, -2.79% decrease in regard to the sequence of the previous years; in regard to 2007 the decrease is -16.43%; and in regard to the period average it is -8.03 %;

- the uses follow the same decreasing trend, the levels of the previous year showing negative differences;

- the domestic consumption availabilities, and the human consumption availability as well are triggered by the paces of this diminution which are correlated;

- from the statistical representation regarding the average pace of the annual variations, we can notice recordings of negative values (between -3.69 and -2.30).

The variance inflation factor (as marker of spreading) shows the existence of a low variation (0-10%), which lays between 6.5 (for uses) and 8.3 (for the available production).

This leads us to the deduction that the level of the actual number can be associated with certain forms of renunciation of milk bovines breeding, expressed by means of the evolutionary level of the markers, observing a decrease of the production availabilities and of the consumption availability. An important role, at least at declarative level, was played by the consequences of a laborious system for the elaboration of the records imposed by the application of the milk quota.

3.2. Medium consumption and foreign trade of milk in Romania

The specific medium consumption for the milk production is indicated by the milk quantities considered as fodder (food for calves) and the industrial processing (with special reference to the dairy products resulted from the processing processes), therefore those products which are either processed, or consumed during the production process.

We can emphasize the following problems from the data presented in Table 3 according to the 2007-2012 dynamics:

Table 3. (Total, Fodder and Industrial processing) medium consumptions for milk in Romania [6]

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	Average/ pace	Standard deviation	Variance inflation factor (%)
Total medium consumption	thousands of hl.	7619	7704	9602	6696	6746	6516	7480.5	1153.7	15.4
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	1.25	0.7	1.01	0.97	-2.84	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	101.11	126.02	87.88	88.54	85.52	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	101.85	102.98	128.36	89.51	90.18	87.1	x	x	x
Fodder consumption	thousands of hl.	6058	6319	7852	4922	4762	4633	5757.7	1244.7	21.6
	in regard to previous year	-	1.04	1.24	0.63	0.97	0.97	-5.23	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	104.3	129.61	81.24	78.6	76.47	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	105.21	109.749	136.37	85.48	82.7	80.46	x	x	x
Industrial processing	thousands of hl.	1561	1385	1750	1774	1984	1883	1722.8	218.0	12.7
	in regard to previous year	-	0.89	1.26	1.01	1.12	0.95	3.80	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	88.72	112.1	113.64	127.09	120.62	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	90.6	80.39	101.57	102.97	115.15	109.29	x	x	x

- the total medium consumption within the analyzed dynamics shows a period of increase, 2007-2009, afterwards, during the next period, 2010-2012, this level decreases. Comparisons with the previous year, 2007 and the period average confirm these variations rendered in percentages;

- the fodder consumption (with reference to the calves' consumption) maintains the same trend in the annual evolution, the level of these consumptions being correlated with the number of animals;

- regarding the industrial milk processing, we can observe the maintenance of the annual variations, but also an increasing trend. The comparisons with the previous year in three of the mentioned years exceed the previous years, in the case of 2012, exceeding 2007 with +20.62%, and with +9.29% in regard to the period average;

- for consumptions, the comparison with the annual paces renders positive results for the industrial processing (of +3.80), but negative for consumptions (of -2.84 for total medium consumption and of -5.23 for fodder consumption). We can also notice a differential fluctuation of the variance inflation factor which can thus be summarized: a medium variation (10-20%) for the total medium consumption (15.4%) and industrial processing (12.7%); a high variation (20-30%) for fodder consumption (21.6%).

Foreign trade, through the import/export chains is considered in the category of resources/uses, in this situation their level and trend differing from the previously analyzed consumptions. The detailed elements presented in *Table 4* analyze this problem, the following aspects being emphasized:

Table 4. Foreign trade (import/export) of milk in Romania [5]

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	Average/ pace	Standard deviation	Variance inflation factor (%)
Import	thousands of hl.	2531	3381	4439	4325	5069	4777	4087.0	952.9	23.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.34	1.31	0.97	1.17	0.94	13.37	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	133.58	175.38	170.88	200.27	188.74	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	61.92	82.72	108.61	105.82	124.02	116.88	x	x	x
Export	thousands of hl.	341	421	646	884	930	1174	732.7	320.8	43.8
	in regard to previous year	-	1.23	1.53	1.37	1.05	1.26	27.81	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	123.46	189.44	259.23	272.72	344.28	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	46.54	57.46	88.17	120.65	126.93	160.23	x	x	x

- the import of milk production/ milk derivatives shows an increasing annual trend, levels which analyzed by comparison signify the following enhancements: in 2010, +17.20 in regard to the previous year, in 2012 the increase is of +88.74 % in comparison with 2007 and +16.88 % in regard to the analyzed average period;

- the export of dairy products records a much lower level, which represents approx. 1/6 of the imports, but the existence of an annual trend rendered by a

much more prominent annual increasing pace. In 2007, a quantity of only 341,000 hl. was exported, and in 2012 the quantity is 1,174,000 hl. All these, analyzed by comparison represent increases which in 2012 are of +26.23% in the sequence of years, +244.28 % in regard to 2007 and +60.23 % in regard to the period average;

- related to the average pace of the foreign trade activities, we observe in the case of the variance inflation factor the existence of positive values which signify a high variation (over 20%) for import/export. But we could mention the fact that the level of export variation is much higher than that of import (the range of the values of the variance inflation factor being of 43.8% and 23.3 %, respectively).

From the analysis of the level of the average annual consumption, we can observe decreases although the total number of milk bovines is at a stable level in the past years which were analyzed. At the same time the import of milk/ dairy derivatives increases, but its pace is by far exceeded by export.

3.3. Food consumptions and the comparative level for milk in Romania

The investigations concerning food consumptions are based on the knowledge of on the one hand, the annual/daily food consumption, and on the other hand, the comparison in time and with the total level of consumption at national level, the form of analysis being expressed in nutrient principles (calories, proteins, glucides and lipids).

The average gross/net consumption for milk rendered in Table 5 emphasizes for the dynamics of the period 2007-2012 levels of the adequate markers, the following being observed:

Table 5. Average annual and daily consumption of milk in Romania [6]

<i>Specification</i>	<i>UM</i>	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	<i>Average/ pace</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Variance inflation factor (%)</i>
Average annual gross consumption	litres/ inhabitant	252.8	254.7	233.2	224.0	227.7	220.3	235.5	14.8	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.71	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.8	92.2	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.2	99.0	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x
Average annual net consumption	kilos/ inhabitant	260.4	262.2	240.2	230.7	234.5	226.9	242.5	15.2	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.72	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.7	92.2	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.1	99.1	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x

Average daily net consumption	grams day/ inhabitant	713.4	718.5	658.1	632.1	642.6	621.7	664.4	41.7	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.71	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.7	92.2	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.1	99.1	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x

- the average annual gross consumption of milk analyzed in the period 2007-2012, shows a variation and we can observe a decreasing pace. Thus, the comparisons of the 2012 level are of -3.25 % in regard to the sequence of years of the period, of -12.86% in regard to the basic year of 2007 and of -6.44% in regard to the average of the analyzed period;

- the average annual net consumption, which is rendered by the level of the presented markers, maintains both the annual variation and the successive decreasing trend, observing a similarity of the data;

- the average daily net consumption also records decreases whose absolute and relative variations by comparison shows the same variation and decreasing trend for the analyzed annual dynamics;

- the interpretation of the statistical representation of the average consumption per inhabitant shows a decrease, the resulting pace being negative (of -2.71 and -2.72), and the variance inflation factor shows a low variation (0-10%), the value of 6.3 being common to all the three forms of average consumption (gross, net and daily).

The analysis was deepened by knowing the consumptions through markers in physical and percentage form, in regard to the principal categories of nutrient principles, calories, proteins, glucides, and lipids, respectively. In *Table 6*, these levels are presented, where we can point up the following problems of the daily food consumption:

Table 6. The comparative level of daily food consumption of milk in Romania [5, 6]

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	Average/pace	Standard deviation	Variance inflation factor (%)
Average daily food consumption, expressed in calories	number calories/ inhabitant	478	481.4	440.9	423.5	430.5	416.5	445.1	28.0	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.72	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100	100.7	92.2	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.1	99.0	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x
	% in regard to total calories at national level	14.1	13.9	12.8	12.5	12.7	12.7	x	x	x
	% in regard to total calories of animal origin	50.8	50.0	47.1	48.0	50.2	49.5	x	x	x

Average daily food consumption, expressed in proteins	grams proteins/ inhabitant	25.0	25.2	23.0	22.1	22.5	21.8	23.3	1.5	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.71	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.7	92.2	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.2	99.0	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x
	% in regard to total proteins at national level	21.8	21.6	20.3	20.2	20.4	20.4	x	x	x
	% in regard to total proteins of animal origin	42.03	41.63	39.16	40.43	42.11	41.68	x	x	x
Average daily food consumption, expressed in glucides	grams glucides / inhabitant	34.2	34.5	31.6	30.3	30.8	29.8	31.9	2.0	6.3
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.71	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.7	92.3	88.6	90.1	87.1	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.4	108.2	99.1	95.1	96.7	93.6	x	x	x
	% in regard to total glucides at national level	7.17	7.23	6.62	6.36	6.46	6.25	x	x	x
	% in regard to total glucides of animal origin	43.0	42.1	39.2	40.1	42.4	41.7	x	x	x
Average daily food consumption, expressed in lipids	grams lipids / inhabitant	25.6	25.9	23.7	22.8	23.1	22.4	23.9	1.5	6.2
	in regard to previous year	-	1.01	0.92	0.96	1.02	0.97	-2.68	x	x
	% in regard to 2007	100.0	100.9	92.4	88.8	90.2	87.3	x	x	x
	% in regard to period average	107.2	108.2	99.1	95.2	96.7	93.6	x	x	x
	% in regard to total lipids at national level	24.5	23.7	21.3	20.3	22.2	21.6	x	x	x
	% in regard to total lipids of animal origin	43.0	42.1	39.2	40.1	42.4	41.7	x	x	x

- the daily food consumption expressed in calories represents a basic marker for food safety, for this reason, the analysis of the period signifying an annual decrease (from 478.0 to 416.5 number of calories per day). This level also implies a decrease by comparison to the percentages of the previous years, to 2007 and the period average (the levels of 2012 being under the comparison limit with -3.26%, with -12.87% and 6.44%, respectively). The comparison is deepened in its comparative form in regard to the national level of calories consumption that also results in a decrease which is displayed both in regard to the total calories at national level (in percentages from 14.08% in 2007 to 12.68% in 2012), and regarding the comparison with the consumption of total calories of animal origin (in percentages from 50.79% in 2007 to 49.52% in 2012);

- the consumption expressed in proteins renders the same annual decrease (from 24.79 in 2007 to 21.76 grams of proteins/inhabitant in 2012), which determines decreases in comparison with the previous year, the basic year 2007 and the period average (which shows decreases similar to the ones

resulted from the analysis of the number of calories). The decrease is also shown by the analysis resulted from the situation of proteins consumption expressed in percentages in comparison with the total consumption at national level (the decreasing variations being for 2007 and 2012 between 21.76% and 20.41%), but also in comparison with the proteins of animal origin (the variations being decreasing for 2007 and 2012 between 42.03% and 41.68%);

- from the analysis of the consumption expressed in glucides the decrease is shown for all the analyses that were made (in absolute values the variations are between 34.24 and 29.84 grams of glucides/inhabitant). The comparisons with the sequences of years, 2007 and the period average show decreases similar to the ones resulted from the analysis of the previous consumption. The comparative representation of milk consumption in regard to the total national consumption of glucides shows decreases in percentages which vary from 7.17 % (year 2007) to 6.25 % (year 2012);

- the average daily food consumption expressed in lipids shows annual fluctuations whose variation is between 25.64 (year 2007) and 22.38 grams of lipids/inhabitant (year 2012). The comparisons made with the sequence of years, basic year 2007 and the period average, shows decreases similar to the ones resulted from the analysis of the previous consumption. The comparisons of the consumption of lipids from milk with the consumption of this nutrient factor at national level shows annual decreases which are between 24.53% (year 2007) and 21.62% (year 2012), the same decreasing trend being recorded by comparison in percentages in regard to the total consumption of lipids of animal origin where the decreases are from 43.02 % (year 2007) to 41.67 % (year 2012);

- For the analysis of the consumption of the principal categories of nutrient principles, calories, proteins, glucides and lipids, respectively, the annual paces, the standard deviation and the variance inflation factor show diminishing levels of consumption resulted from the forms of average consumption (gross, net and daily).

From the above, it results that there is decreasing food consumption, this being shown in a quantitative form in regard to the gross and net consumption, but also in a qualitative form resulting from the balance between the principal categories of nutrient factors, calories, proteins, glucides and lipids, respectively. The difference is observed as well in the pace of variations resulted from the annual levels of the markers and operations in use.

Conclusions

Romania's potential for milk and dairy products is based on the evaluation of the production potential and its target, which emphasizes the dimension of the resources and the structure of the consumptions, the following can be emphasized:

(1) Regarding the production potential, rendered by the number of cows, buffalo cows and heifers, we can observe a decreasing trend shown by the same decrease and variation of the annual levels of the annual productions of milk. The statistical interpretation shows the existence of a medium variation for the total numbers, and a low variation for production.

(2) We observe that the level of available production and the consumption decrease. This can be partially justified by the correlation which is shown in the lack of evidence and self-consumption of the milk productions. The levels of the variance inflation factor, as marker of spreading, lies within the limits of a low variation.

(3) The structure which is represented by the principal elements of the medium consumptions shows annual paces, whose levels and trends are differentiated. For instance, the quantities of milk used as fodder are decreasing, and for industrial processing we can observe increases. Statistically, we remark the existence of a differentiated fluctuation: medium variations for the total medium consumption and industrial processing, and a high variation for the fodder consumption.

(4) On the whole, foreign trade with milk/ milk derivatives shows an increasing trend, the paces being differentiated. Thus, the import records much higher than export (the levels of export being of approx. 1/6 of imports), but the pace of increase of export is much prominent than export. Related to the statistical representation of these markers we can observe that the average pace of foreign trade activities has positive values, which means a high variation. But by means of the fluctuations of the variance inflation factor, resulting in positive values, we observe a high variation for the export activities which exceed by far those of import.

(5) The annual and daily average consumption for milk/milk derivatives show variations with the trend of a decreasing pace. Regarding the annual average gross and net consumption, rendered by the level of the markers presented, we observe the maintenance of an annual variation but also the successive decreasing trend, noticing a similarity of the data level.

(6) The analysis of the comparative level of the daily food consumption for milk, expressed in calories and the principal categories of nutrient factors (proteins, glucides and lipids), by a representation in percentages of annual structures, signifies a decrease. In the statistical representation of the analysis of the average consumption per inhabitant we can also observe a decrease, the resulting pace being negative, and the variance inflation factor shows a low variation. The same representations are maintained (in regard to the diminished

levels of consumptions) also in the structure of the consumption of the principal categories of nutrient factors, calories, proteins, glucides, and lipids, respectively.

This decreasing trend is substantiated both by the results of the annual comparisons of the level of markers for milk in the dynamics and the sequence of years, of year 2007 and the period average, and also in comparison with the structure of consumptions expressed in calories and the principal categories of nutrient factors at total national level and of those of animal origin.

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